

Project ID N°: **101036449**

Call: **H2020-LC-GD-2020-3**

Topic: **LC-GD-8-1-2020** - Innovative, systemic zero-pollution solutions to protect health, environment, and natural resources from persistent and mobile chemicals

Preventing Recalcitrant Organic Mobile Industrial chemicals for Circular Economy in the soil-sediment-water System

Start date of the project: **1st November 2021**

Duration: **42 months**

D4.5 – Mass flow and fate analysis for PFAS from landfill leachate in Bulgaria and Italy

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Lead Beneficiary: **UNIVPM**

Type of delivery: **R**

Dissemination Level: **PU**

Filename and version: **PROMISCES_D4-5_PFAS-Mass-Flow-Analysis (version 2)**

Website: **<https://promisces.eu/>**

Due date: **31 October 2023 [M24]**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N°101036449

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Document History

This document has been through the following revisions:

Version	Date	Author	Description
0.1	13/10/2023	Nicola Lancioni, Elisa Blumenthal, Massimiliano Sgroi, Francesco Fatone	Complete draft of the deliverable
0.2	20/10/2023	Michael Stapf	Official document review
0.3	24/10/2023	Alessandro Frugis, Marco Lazzazzara	Revision of the document
0.4	27/10/2023	Nicola Lancioni, Elisa Blumenthal, Massimiliano Sgroi, Francesco Fatone	Final version of the document
0.5	30/10/2023	Massimiliano Sgroi	Final version for approval
1	30/10/2023	Julie Lions	Version
1.1	29/02/2024	Irina Ribarova, Dobril Valchev. Valentina Lubomirova, Stilyana Lincheva, Alessandro Frugis	Complete Draft of UNISOFIA contribution
1.2	17/04/2024	Michael Stapf	Quality control review for UNISOFIA contribution
1.3	23/04/2024	Irina Ribarova	Addressing quality check comments for UNISOFIA contribution
1.4	26/04/2024	Yuki Bartels	Additional quality check comments for UNISOFIA contribution
1.4	27/04/2024	Irina Ribarova	Addressing additional comments for UNISOFIA contribution
1.5	29/04/2024	Massimiliano Sgroi	Merging of UNISOFIA contribution and Final version for approval
2	30/04/2024	Julie Lions	Version

Authorisation

Authorisation	Name	Status	Date
Review of version 0.2	Michael Stapf	Expert in the field	23/10/2023
Validation of version 0.5	Ulf Miehe	WP leader	23/10/2023
Quality Control of version 0.5	Julie Lions	Project Coordinator	30/10/2023
Approval of version 1	Julie Lions	Project Coordinator	30/10/2023
Review of version 1.2	Michael Stapf	Expert in the field	17/04/2024
Review of version 1.4	Yuki Bartels	Expert in the field	26/04/2024
Validation of version 1.5	Ulf Miehe	WP leader	29/04/2024
Quality Control of version 1.5	Julie Lions	Project Coordinator	30/04/2024
Approval of version 2	Julie Lions	Project Coordinator	30/04/2024

Distribution

This document has been distributed to:

Name	Title	Version issued	Date of issue
UNIVPM, ACEA, SIMAM, UNISOFIA, KWB	Task 4.4 partners	Version 1	30/10/2023
UNIVPM, ACEA, SIMAM, UNISOFIA, KWB	Task 4.4 partners	Version 2	30/04/2024

Executive Summary

This document is the result of Subtask 4.4.1 “Mass balance of PFAS transformation pathways during conventional full-scale leachate treatment” of WP4 of the H2020 PROMISCES project. Particularly, this report documents the occurrence and fate of PFAS during landfill leachate treatment and management in different study sites in Italy and Bulgaria with the aim to identify the most critical pathways of PFAS contamination for the environment through landfill leachate management.

In Italy, three full-scale landfill leachate treatment plants (LTP) were investigated in three different regions of the country (i.e., Marche, Veneto, Liguria) to perform mass flow analysis of PFAS compounds. In two of the investigated landfill leachate plants (LTP1 and LTP2) are implemented conventional leachate treatments (i.e., clari-flocculation, biological process, ultrafiltration), whereas in a third plant (LTP3) are utilized advanced technologies (i.e., reverse osmosis).

In Bulgaria, ten landfills were selected, which are representative in terms of geographical location, age and treatment capacity within the country, to investigate occurrence of PFAS in the produced leachate. In addition, a complete mass flow analysis was accomplished along the conventional treatment plant that treat the landfill leachate produced at the Sofia landfill facilities, which receive wastes from about 24% of the country's population.

To perform mass balance studies, targeted sampling strategies were conducted at the Italian and Bulgarian study sites to consider the effect of operational parameters (e.g., HRT, SRT) on PFAS mass load calculation.

Results of the investigation showed that almost the entire load of PFAS measured in the influent landfill leachate remained in the liquid phase after treatments (conventional or advanced). Hence, the high load of PFAS compounds in the effluents constitute a threat for water reuse application and for the environmental status of the receiving water bodies.

Advanced treatment such as reverse osmosis (RO) are able to remove PFAS from landfill leachate. Nevertheless, appropriate technologies for treating RO concentrates need to be implemented to prevent PFAS from being spread into the environment by the concentrate discharge.

In terms of mass balance calculations, agreement between the load of PFAS compounds entering the plant and PFAS exiting the plant was observed only in LTP3 in Italy, where only physical and chemical treatments are utilized for leachate treatment. Probably, the presence of biological process in the other leachate treatment plants was the reason of precursor transformation and/or of PFAS adsorption/desorption processes, which produced a discrepancy between load and type of PFAS compounds entering and exiting the plant.

Furthermore, this study provides a first insight into the occurrence of PFAS in landfill leachates produced in Bulgarian landfills in terms of concentration and types. In the leachates from the ten landfills only seven out of the 30 analysed PFAS were detected above the LOQ of 1 µg/L. These PFAS were PFBA, PFBS, PFHxA, PFPeA, PFOA, PFOS and 4:2 FTSA. The results show that the PFAS concentrations in untreated leachate in Bulgaria are within the typical European range of 0.005 to 18 µg/L.

In this report, the first part of the document (**section 1**) gives an introduction to the topic by discussing possible routes of contamination into the environment through landfill leachate management and presenting an overview of reported PFAS concentrations in landfill leachate worldwide. In addition, the objectives of the investigation are defined.

Section 2 describes the methodology used for the accomplishment of the work. It lists the investigated landfills in Bulgaria and describes the schematics of the selected leachate treatment plants to perform PFAS mass balance in both the countries. In addition, in this section are illustrated the sampling strategies implemented to perform accurate mass flow analysis. Then, all analytical methods used to measure PFAS or to characterise leachate and sludge are described.

The third section (**section 3**) reports and critically discusses the obtained results and the conclusions of the investigation are reported in **section 4**.

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List of Abbreviations

PFAS LIST	NAME	CAS-NUMBER
PFDA	Perfluorodecanoic acid	335-76-2
PFHPA	Perfluoroheptanoic acid	375-85-9
PFHXS	Perfluorohexane sulfonic acid	355-46-4
PFNA	Acid perfluorononanoique	375-95-1
PFOA	Perfluorooctanoic acid	335-67-1
PFOS	Perfluorooctane sulfonic acid	1763-23-1
PFDODA	Perfluorododecanoic acid	307-55-1
PFDODS	Perfluorododecane sulfonic acid	79780-39-5
PFDS	Perfluorodecane sulfonic acid	335-77-3
PFHPS	Perfluoroheptane acid	375-92-8
PFHXA	Perfluorohexanoic acid	307-24-4
PFPEA	Perfluoropentanoic acid	2706-90-3
PFTRDA	Acid perfluorotridecanoique	72629-94-8
PFTEDA	Perfluorotetradecanoic acid	376-06-7
PFUNDA	Perfluoroundecanoic acid	2058-94-8
PFBA	Perfluorobutanoic acid	375-22-4
PFBS	Perfluorobutane sulfonic acid	375-73-5 or 59933-66-3
4:2 FTSA	4 :2 fluorotelomer sulfonic acid	757124-72-4
6:2 FTSA	6 :2 fluorotelomer sulfonic acid	27619-97-2
8:2 FTSA	8 :2 fluorotelomer sulfonic acid	39108-34-4
NADONA	4,8-dioxa-3H-perfluorononanoic acid	958445-44-8
ETFOSAA	N-Ethyl perfluorooctane sulfonamido acetic acid	1336-61-4 or 2991-50-6
PFOSA	Perfluorooctane sulfonamide	754-91-6
MEFOSAA	N-Methyl perfluorooctane sulfonamido acetic acid	2355-31-9
PFNS	Perfluorononane sulfonic acid	68259-12-1
PFPEs	perfluoropentane sulfonic acid	2706-91-4
PFTRDS	Perfluorotridecane sulfonic acid	174675-49-1
PFUNDS	perfluoroundecane sulfonic acid	749786-16-1
HFPO-DA (= GENX)	hexafluoropropylene oxide dimer acid /perfluoro-2-propoxypropanoic acid	13252-13-6
C604	Acetic acid, 2,2-difluoro-2-[[2,2,4,5-tetrafluoro-5-(trifluoromethoxy) -1,3-dioxolan-4-yl]oxy]-, ammonium salt (1 :1)	1190931-27-1

PFAS = Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances

CE = Circular economy

PM = Persistent and mobile

TRL = Technology readiness level

EIS = Extracted Internal Standard

LC-MS/MS = Liquid Chromatography with tandem mass spectrometry

MRM = multiple reaction monitoring

HRT = Hydraulic retention time

SRT = Sludge retention time

MB = Method Blanks

RB = Reagent Blanks

LOQ = Limit of Quantitation

LTP = leachate treatment plant

WWTP = wastewater treatment plant

RDF = Refuse Derived Fuel

SBR = Sequencing batch reactor

SBS = Sodium biphenyl

TF = Total fluorine

TPSiF = Fluorotriphenylsilane

1. Introduction

1.1. PFAS occurrence in landfill leachate and related emissions to the environment

The types of PFAS-containing products are extremely different. Consumer goods like carpets, fabrics, clothing, packaging, food wrappers, and even cleaning and personal care products that are stain- and water-resistant contain PFAS (Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2018). In landfills, PFAS precursors such as fluorotelomer-based coatings on carpet, clothing and food packaging are biologically transformed into stable and more mobile PFAS (Hamid et al., 2020). The short and long-chain PFAS are defined as persistent, mobile, and potentially toxic (PM(T)) substances.

Table 1 provides an overview of the occurrence of PFAS in landfill leachate worldwide. Reported PFAS concentrations range from a few micrograms per liter up to 500 µg/L as the sum of detected PFAS (Σ PFAS). These data are directly influenced by the number of target PFAS and precursors investigated. Lang et al. (2017) distinguished the concentrations of PFAS in landfill leachate as a function of climate conditions and waste age: higher concentrations were detected in leachate produced by young waste and under wet weather conditions. Yan et al., (2015) reported PFAS concentrations ranging from 7 to 290 µg/L in Chinese landfill leachate. Wei et al., (2019) carried out a review on the presence of PFAS in several landfills worldwide, and they found that in Europe PFAS concentrations in landfill leachates generally range from 0.005 to 18 µg/L. Masoner et al. (2020) pointed out that disposal of treated leachate into wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) can contribute substantially to the increase of PFAS concentrations in the wastewater influents. Knutsen et al., (2019) and Helmer et al., (2022) found out that leachate from young landfills tends to have a higher presence of short-chain PFAS than older landfills, due to industrial bans on long-chain PFAS in the recent years. Moreover, short-chain PFAS have higher solubility and lower sorptivity than long-chain PFAS. Finally, some trends between PFAS, landfill characteristics (e.g. landfill age, waste type, climate, etc.) and leachate parameters such as pH and TOC have been reported in some literature studies (Benskin et al., 2012; Gallen et al., 2017).

Table 1: PFAS occurrence in landfill leachates worldwide

REFERENCE	Detected PFAS and precursors	SOURCE (n = number of investigated landfill)	ΣPFAS CONCENTRATION (µg/L)
(Lang et al., 2017)	PFBA, PFPeA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, 6:2 FTCA, 8:2 FTCA, 7:3 FTCA, PFBS, PFHxS, PFOS, 6:2 FTSA, 8:2 FTSA, MeFBSAA, MeFOSAA and EtFOSAA	Landfill with Wet weather	Waste age < 10 years: 15 ± 16 µg/L; Waste age >10 years: 11 ± 12 µg/L
		Landfill with Temperate weather	Waste age < 10 years: 7 ± 1 µg/L; Waste age >10 years: 11 ± 9 µg/L
		Landfill with Arid weather	Waste age < 10 years: 29 ± 1 µg/L; Waste age >10 years: 2 ± 0,8 µg/L
(Yan et al., 2015)	PFPra, PFPeA, PFBA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnA, PFDoA, PFTA, PFBS, PFHxS, PFOS.	Landfill in China	7-290
(Wei et al., 2019)	PFBS, PFPeS, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS, PFDCs, FTCA, PFPrA, PFBA, PFPeA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnA, PFDoA, PFOSA, FTSA	Landfill in North America	0.5 – 32
		Landfill in Europe	0.005 – 18
		Landfill in Australia	0.03 – 17
		Landfill in China	3 – 300
(Masoner et al., 2020)	36 PFAS	Landfills in Florida (n = 3)	21 – 49
(Propp et al., 2021)	PFBA, PFPeA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnA, PDFoDA, PFTriDA, PFTeDA, PFBS, PFHxS, PFOS, PFDS, PFECHS, FOSA	Landfill in Canada	13
(Knutsen et al., 2019)	PFBA, PFPeA, PFHxA, PFBS, PFHpA, HPFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PF-3,7-DMOA, PFUnDA, PFDoA, PFTra, PFTA, PFHxDA, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS and PFDS. 4:2 FTSA, 6:2 FTSA, 8:2 FTSA, 8:2 FTOH, FOSA, EtFOSA, MeFOSA, EtFOSE and MeFOSE.	Landfills in Norway (n = 10)	0.3 – 11
(Helmer et al., 2022)	PFBS, PFBA, PFPeS, PFPeA, PFHxS, PFHxA, PFHpS, PFHpA, FOSA, PFOS, PFOA, PFNS, PFNA, PFDS, PFDA, PFUnA/PFUdA, PFDoA, PFTeDA, PFHxDA.	Landfills in Michigan (n = 19)	0.2 – 540
(Benskin et al., 2012)	PFBS, PFHxS, PFOS, PFDS, PFBA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFDoDA, PFTDA, FOSA, FOSAA, MeFOSAA, EtFOSAA, 6:2 FTCA, 8:2 FTCA, 10:2 FTCA, 6:2 FTUCA, 8:2 FTUCA and 10:2 FTUCA	Canadian landfills (n = 2)	2.5 -36
(Stoiber et al., 2020)	9 PFAS	Australian Landfills (n = 27)	0.2 – 46
	14 PFAS	Chinese Landfills (n = 5)	7.3 -292
	29 PFAS	Chinese Landfills (n = 3)	22 -39
	43 PFAS	German Landfills (n = 22)	0.03 – 13
	70 PFAS	USA Landfills (n = 18)	0.3 – 66
	11 PFAS	USA Landfills (n = 5)	2.8 – 18
(Gallen et al., 2017)	PFOA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFDoDA and PFHxS.	Australian Landfills (n = 27)	1.2 – 30

Globally, landfills are considered to be one of the major sources of PFAS contamination to the environment. In landfills, PFAS-based products can release these compounds into leachate and even into the air (ITRC, 2020). It is common practice to discharge landfill leachate, after some treatment, to municipal WWTPs. Conventional WWTPs have demonstrated to be ineffective at removing PFAS and the presence of precursors in the influent may lead to an increase of PFAS concentrations in the effluent after biological transformation (Lenka et al., 2021). Thus, PFAS from landfill leachate may be released to the aquatic environment via WWTP effluents, but can also be adsorbed into municipal sewage sludge limiting its agronomic reutilization (Fredriksson et al., 2022; Helmer et al., 2022).

Finally, some researchers (Yan et al., 2015) estimated that the Chinese national leakage of PFAS to groundwater from landfill leachate may be 3110 kg/year as Σ PFAS, which is a significant release that can potentially pose a serious threat to the human health.

1.2. Objectives of the research activities

High PFAS loads from landfill leachates reaching municipal WWTPs prevents proper treatment and ultimately hinders zero pollution discharge and further water reuse due to higher PFAS discharges from WWTPs. This research aims to determine the occurrence of PFAS in landfill leachates and to identify the fate of PFAS during full-scale conventional and advanced treatments of this liquid waste. Hence, mass flow analysis of PFAS compounds were carried out in three full-scale leachate treatment plants in Italy, and in one full-scale leachate treatment plant in Bulgaria to identify the most critical pathways of PFAS contamination to the environment. During leachate treatment, PFAS may accumulate in the sludge or remain in the liquid phase that is typically mixed with the raw wastewater influent of a municipal WWTP. If advanced treatments such as reverse osmosis (RO) are used to treat landfill leachate, most of the PFAS may remain in the concentrate, which needs to be properly treated.

To date, PFAS-contaminated sewage sludge and RO concentrate from landfill leachate treatment are currently transported to incineration plants or disposed of in waste landfills. However, these practices are not sustainable and do not aim to recover resources.

The present study aims to provide a valuable assessment of the state of the art related to landfill leachate treatment and management, which will be used in the next PROMISCES research activities to develop innovative approaches to treat landfill leachate and obtain a near zero pollution discharge.

Furthermore, this research aims to provide a first insight into the occurrence of PFAS in landfill leachate produced in Bulgarian landfills, where very limited data are available at national level.

2. Methodology

2.1. Study sites in Italy

This section describes the full-scale leachate treatment plants that have been selected in Italy to evaluate the mass balances and fate of PFAS compounds. Particularly, two conventional leachate treatment plants and one advanced treatment plant have been selected for the study.

2.1.1 Leachate treatment plant N°1 (Italy)

The leachate treatment plant N°1 (LTP) is located in Marche Region, Italy, and it treats non-hazardous liquid wastes such as landfill leachate, sewage sludge from septic tanks and waste derived from sewer cleaning. The leachate represents around the 46% of the non-hazardous liquid wastes treated by the plant. The effluent of the LTP is mixed with the influent of the municipal WWTP. Thus, the LTP can be considered as “plant in a plant” (Figure 1). The municipal WWTP treats about 7 million m³ of wastewater per year and has a capacity of 60.000 population equivalents.

Figure 1. Leachate treatment plant N°1.

The LTP consists of pre-treatment, primary sedimentation, biological treatment, secondary sedimentation, and tertiary treatment (ultrafiltration) to reduce macro-pollutants loads (COD, TSS, TN and TP) before the discharge into the WWTP. Landfill leachate and other liquid wastes are previously collected in an equalization tank with a volume of 300 m³ and a hydraulic retention time (HRT) of around 4 days (flow rate 170 ± 65 m³/d). The pre-treatment consists of screening and degritting, followed by an accumulation tank and then coagulation, flocculation, and clarification units. The hydraulic retention time (HRT) of the whole physical-chemical treatments (screening and degritting, flocculation and clarification) is 46 h. After the clarification there is an equalization tank, which has a volume of 160 m³ and a HRT of 18 h. It distributes the water to two biological reactors, which have a total volume of 1000 m³, a HRT of 110 h and a sludge retention time (SRT) of 43 d. Biological treatment is followed by a secondary sedimentation, operated in a sedimentation tank with a volume of 172 m³ and a HRT of 19 h. After the secondary sedimentation, two ultrafiltration membrane modules are operated in two tanks with a volume of 21 m³ and a HRT of 5 h, each. They are followed by a further equalization/storage tank with a volume of 21 m³, which sends the treated water to the municipal WWTP.

The sludge from the secondary sedimentation is recirculated to the biological reactors and transferred to the thickening centrifuges, together with the chemical sludge. The supernatant is returned to the equalization tank upstream of the biological reactors. The thickened sludge is disposed of at a landfill for hazardous waste. The amount of biological and chemical sludge produced is about 12 m³/d and 2 m³/d, respectively. The amount of sludge disposed of is about 1.2 t/d. The process overview of LTP N°1 is given in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Process overview of the leachate treatment plant N°1.

2.1.2 Leachate treatment plant N°2 (Italy)

The LTP N°2 is located in Veneto region, Italy. A satellite image of the plant is shown in Figure 3. The liquid wastes that the LTP is authorized to treat are classified by the EER codes:

- 02 (wastes from agriculture, horticulture, aquaculture, forestry, hunting and fishing, food preparation and processing),
- 08 (wastes from the manufacture, formulation, supply and use of coatings, adhesives, sealants and printing inks),
- 19 (wastes from waste management facilities, off-site wastewater treatment plants and the preparation of water intended for human consumption and water for industrial use), and
- 20 (municipal wastes, including separately collected fractions).

Figure 3. Leachate treatment plant N°2

The maximum amount of liquid waste that can be treated in the LTP is 150,000 t/year and 600 t/d. Leachate represents 30% of the whole liquid waste treated. At LTP N°2, the landfill leachate and other liquid wastes collected from the sewage system are sent to screening and degritting units, and then to a 400 m³ accumulation tank. The physical-chemical pre-treatment of liquid waste is currently not used. After the accumulation tank (HRT about 1 d), the leachate and the other liquid wastes enter the biological reactor. The biological treatment consists of an oxidation-denitrification process, which takes place in a “carousel” reactor with a volume of 1450 m³. The biological reactor has a HRT of 4.9 d. The effluent from the biological reactor goes to a secondary settler with a surface area of 200 m² and a volume of 500 m³. The sludge is recirculated to the biological reactor. The HRT of the secondary clarifier is 1.7 d. The effluent from the secondary clarifier is sent to the municipal WWTP, where it is treated together with the municipal wastewater. The total HRT of the leachate treatment plant is 6.5 d, whereas the HRT of the municipal WWTP is 5.2 d.

The SRTs are about 18 and 32 days for the LTP and the municipal WWTP, respectively. The excess sludge of the LTP from the secondary settlers goes to an aerobic digester, where it is digested together with the sewage sludge coming from the municipal WWTP. The aerobic digester has a volume of 1010 m³. After digestion, the sludge is treated by thickening and dewatering processes, and is finally disposed to landfill. The supernatant from the thickening and the dewatering processes is returned to the WWTP influent. The sludge produced is about 4.5 t/d. The process overview of LTP N°2 is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Layout of leachate treatment plant N°2.

2.1.3 Leachate treatment plant N°3 (Italy)

The LTP N°3 is located in Liguria region, Italy. It is a mobile plant, which was constructed for treating the leachate coming from the nearby landfill in continuous operation (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Leachate treatment plant N°3.

The landfill leachate is first collected in a 40m³ accumulation tank (0.4 h HRT). From the accumulation tank, the leachate goes through a flotation unit, a sand filtration unit and then, it is then treated by ultrafiltration (UF) membranes. Solids and wastes from the flotation, sand filters and UF units are treated by a vacuum filtration and then disposed of at the landfill. The permeate from the UF membranes goes to a 88 m³ tank (0.8 h HRT). From there, it goes to a double-pass reverse osmosis (RO1 and RO2) process with a treatment capacity of 100 m³/h, operating in two parallel lines (50 m³/h each). The concentrate from the second pass RO2 is recirculated to the first RO1 (Figure 6). In contrast, the concentrate produced by the double-pass system is sent to an accumulation tank and treated by another RO unit (ROx), working in double-pass configuration. The permeate from the second stage RO (ROx) is sent to the RO2 membrane, whereas the concentrate is treated by physical-chemical processes (clari-flocculation to remove metals and COD), sand filters and ammonia stripping and scrubbing. Both the final permeate from the RO system and the effluent from the concentrate treatment line are discharged to the sewer system.

The chemical sludge produced by the physical-chemical process is sent to a thickener and a filter press, which recirculates the supernatant to the physical-chemical reactor for RO concentrate treatment. The process overview of LTP N°3 is shown in Figure 6. The total HRT of the LTP is about 24 hours. The total annual production of solids from vacuum filtration and chemical sludge from concentrate line is 2900 and 1825 t/year, respectively.

Figure 6. Block diagram of the leachate treatment plant N°3.

2.2. Sampling strategy in Italy

2.2.1 Sampling at leachate treatment plant N°1 (Italy)

Selected sampling points at LTP N°1 are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Process overview and sampling points of leachate treatment plant N°1.

Sampling points were selected to perform mass balance calculations of PFAS in each treatment unit and along the entire LTP. Grab samples were collected from different accumulation tanks, where the liquid waste was already equalized and homogenized. In contrast, 24 hours composite sample were taken at the effluent of the UF unit (sampling point 4 in Figure 7) to be representative of at least one day of plant operation. Grab samples were collected for solid matrices. The sampling was repeated after 5 days within the same sampling campaign, with the scope to take into account possible effects on PFAS transformation by the biological treatments, which have an HRT of 5 days. The time interval between two consecutive sampling campaigns was around 40/60 days, which is a comparable to the SRT of the biological process. In total, four sampling campaigns were carried out (Table 2).

Table 2. Sampling campaign for leachate treatment plant N°1.

Sampling point	Description	Sample Type	N. Samples	Frequency
SP1	Accumulation tank (HRT of 70 hours)	Grab sample in the tank (liquid)	2	Every 5 days
SP1	Accumulation tank (HRT of 70 hours)	Grab sample in the tank (solid)	2	Every 5 days
SP2	Effluent Clarification/Influent Biological reactor	Grab sample (liquid) in equalization tank	2	Every 5 days
SP3	Effluent Secondary Sedimentation	Grab sample (liquid)	2	Every 5 days
SP4	Effluent Ultrafiltration	Composite sample (liquid) (24h)	2	Every 5 days
SP5	Chemical Sludge	Grab sample (solid)	2	Every 5 days
SP6	Sewage sludge	Grab sample (solid)	2	Every 5 days
SP7	Dewatered sludge	Grab sample (solid)	2	Every 5 days
SP8	Supernatant	Grab sample (liquid)	2	Every 5 days
Total samples per sampling campaign			18	
Total samples in all sampling campaigns (n = 4)			72	

2.2.2 Sampling at leachate treatment plant N°2 (Italy)

Selected sampling points at LTP N°2 are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Process overview and sampling points of leachate treatment plant N°2.

Sampling points were selected to perform mass balance calculations of PFAS in each treatment unit and along the entire LTP. Grab samples were collected from the accumulation tanks, where the liquid waste was equalized and homogenized. In contrast, 24 hours composite samples were taken at the effluent of secondary sedimentations as well as at the influent and effluent of the municipal WWTP (sampling points 2, 3 and 4 in Figure 8) to be representative of at least one day of plant operation. Grab samples were collected for solid matrices. The sampling was repeated after 6 days within the same sampling campaign to account for possible effects on PFAS transformation by the biological treatment, which has an HRT of around 6 days in this LTP. The time interval between two consecutive sampling campaigns was around 60 days, which is longer than the SRT of the biological process. In total, two sampling campaigns were carried out (Table 3).

Table 3. Sampling campaign for leachate treatment plant N°2.

Sampling Point	Description	Sample Type	N. Samples	Frequency
SP1	Accumulation tank (HRT = 32 hours)	Grab sample in the tank (liquid)	2	Every 6 days
SP2	Accumulation tank (HRT = 32 hours)	Grab sample in the tank (solid)	2	Every 6 days
SP2	Effluent secondary sedimentation	Composite sample (24h) (liquid)	2	Every 6 days
SP5	Sewage sludge	In the tank (solid)	2	Every 6 days
SP6	Municipal Sewage sludge	In the tank (solid)	2	Every 6 days
SP8	Dewatered sludge	In the tank (solid)	2	Every 6 days
SP7	Supernatant	Grab (liquid)	2	Every 6 days
SP3	Influent WWTP	Composite sample (24h) (liquid)	2	Every 6 days
SP4	Effluent WWTP	Composite sample (24h) (liquid)	2	Every 6 days
Total samples per sampling campaign			18	
Total samples in all sampling campaigns (n = 2)			36	

2.2.3 Sampling at leachate treatment plant N°3 (Italy)

Selected sampling points at the LTP N°3 are shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Process overview and sampling points of leachate treatment plant N°3.

The different sampling points were selected for accomplishing a mass balance within the different treatment units and along the entire plant. Two sampling campaigns were carried out during this study. In each sampling campaign, a total number of 8 samples were collected. Details are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Sampling campaign for leachate treatment plant N°3.

Sampling Point	Description	Sample Type	N. Samples
SP1	Accumulation tank	Grab sample in the tank (liquid)	1
SP2	Disposal after vacuum filtration	Grab sample	1
SP3	Effluent UF	Grab sample (liquid)	1
SP4	Effluent RO permeate	Grab sample (liquid)	1
SP5	Influent Physical-chemical reactor	Grab sample	1
SP8	Dewatered sludge	Grab sample (solid)	1
SP6	Influent Stripping/Scrubber	Grab sample	1
SP7	Effluent Stripping/Scrubber	Grab sample	1
Total samples per sampling campaign			8
Total samples in all sampling campaigns (n = 2)			16

2.3. Study sites in Bulgaria

2.3.1 Selection of ten landfills

There are 55 officially registered regional municipal landfills in Bulgaria. The data available for them is limited and often contradictory. Initial screening was conducted using the annual performance reports. Landfills that reported the occurrence of TF were contacted first. Given the importance of membrane treatment for data collection for plasma experiments, this was included as a further selection criterion. As not all of the contacted landfills agreed to participate in the study, the initial list based on these two criteria was expanded. In total, approximately half of the existing regional municipal landfills were contacted. Once the requisite number of 10 landfills had agreed to participate, the selection procedure was terminated. The landfills included in the study are shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Regional landfills included in the study (population served is given in parentheses)

The landfills selected for this study are representative for Bulgaria in terms of geographical location, age and treatment capacity.

Most of the landfills in Bulgaria are relatively young, having been constructed within the last 15 years with financial support from the government and the EU Cohesion Fund. The selected landfills were constructed between 2009 (e.g. Lovech) and 2019 (e.g. Blagoevgrad), covering a range of ages from 4 to 15-year-old landfills. They display the variety of sizes of the Bulgarian regional landfills, serving populations from 20,000 to 1,300,000 inhabitants. Additionally, the selected sites account for approximately 35% of the total waste landfilled in Bulgaria annually.

2.3.2 Leachate treatment plant for mass flow analysis (Sofia)

A mass flow analysis on PFAS was conducted for the largest landfill for municipal wastes that serves the Sofia municipality (referred to as the Sofia landfill in this deliverable).

The solid waste collection and treatment plant of Sofia currently accepts the following wastes in accordance with the national Waste Classification Ordinance (Ordinance N2/23.07.2014 for classification of the wastes):

- 18 - Waste from human or veterinary healthcare and/or related research activities (excluding kitchen waste and waste from restaurants not directly generated by healthcare activities).
- 19 - Wastes from waste treatment facilities; waste from wastewater treatment plants, generated outside their generation; waste from water purification for drinking and industrial use.
- 20 - Municipal waste (from household and similar), including separate collection.

The Sofia solid waste plant has a total capacity of 3,234,000 tonnes and can handle up to 450 tonnes per day of waste in solid aggregate form, including separated collected fractions from commercial,

industrial, and administrative activities. The Sofia landfill facilities treat waste from about 24% of the country's population using a conventional treatment scheme (mechanical and biological stage).

A satellite image of the Sofia landfill is shown in Figure 11. The solid waste enters the receiving bunker first. The solid wastes suitable for recycling and Refuse Derived Fuel (RDF) are separated in the installations of the Sofia solid waste plant, and the remaining fraction is then sent to the landfill cell.

Figure 11: The site of the Sofia landfill

Figure 11 and Figure 12 depict the two leachate treatment plants (LTPs) available at the site. LTP1 treats the landfill leachate, while LTP2 treats the leachate from the receiving bunker and mainly condensate generated during the production of RDF.

Figure 12: Flows at Sofia solid waste collection and treatment plants

A mass flow analysis was conducted for the LTP1, which is presented in more detail in Figure 13.

Figure 13: The technological scheme of LTP1 for treatment of leachate

The technology used for treatment of the leachate follows the conventional method for treating municipal wastewater. This involves a mechanical stage that includes sieves and grit chambers, followed by biological treatment in sequencing batch reactors (SBRs), lamella clarifiers and rapid sand filters.

2.4. Sampling strategy in Bulgaria

2.4.1 Sampling at the ten landfills

Grab samples of the leachate were collected from the equalization tanks located at the inlet of the treatment units when it was available on site or from the retention reservoirs for leachate recirculation back to the landfill when leachate was not treated on site. Two sampling campaigns were conducted for each landfill, except for: i) Burgas, where only one sample was taken in October 2023 because the agreement was obtained late, and ii) Sofia where in addition to these two campaigns, four more sampling campaigns were conducted. The first campaign was conducted in September 2023 and the second in October-November 2023.

In Figure 14 pictures of the local leachate treatment plant in Blagoevgrad and the retention reservoir in Lovech are shown as an example.

A. The local leachate treatment plant in Blagoevgrad

B. The retention reservoir in Lovech

Figure 14: Setup at two of the studied landfills (A & B)

2.4.2 Sampling at leachate treatment plant Sofia (LTP1)

Grab samples were collected from various sampling points of LTP1 (shown in Figure 12 and Figure 13) to perform mass balance calculations of PFAS in the treatment units and along the entire plant. In total, 7 sampling points were selected:

- Sampling point 1: Leachate from the bunker that is treated in LTP2 and used for cooling. The drainage after cooling goes to LTP1 (Sampling point 3).
- Sampling point 2: Leachate from the landfill cells, after retention in the equalization tank
- Sampling point 3: Drainage after cooling and retention in equalization tank
- Sampling point 4: Mechanically treated leachate in LTP1 before biological stage
- Sampling point 5: Biologically treated leachate before sand filtration (it was not kept after the first sampling campaign due to the sand filter being out of operation)
- Sampling point 6: Treated leachate prior discharge into the receiving water body
- Sampling point 7: Non-dewatered excess sludge from the biological stage

The samples were collected in plastic bottles (HDPE) and refrigerated until they were sent to ACEA in boxes using coolers.

Six sampling campaigns were conducted over a 10-week period (71 days) from 30th October 2023 to 9th January 2024, with a two-week interval between each campaign. The sampling duration and interval was determined based on the hydraulic retention time of the entire plant. The main challenge for the mass balance is the disconnect between inflow and effluent concentrations due to:

1. **High fluctuation of leachate flow** (sampling point 2): depending on the rainfall, the flow may vary between 5 and 35 m³/d;
2. **Long retention time in the overall system**: equalization tank for leachate (600 m³), volume of the sequencing batch reactor (SBR) (600 m³ - 3 SBRs, 200 m³ each) and equalization tanks after the lamella clarifier (200 m³), which results in a retention time in the whole system of greater than 4 months during dry weather periods.

The average leachate flow rate during the studied period was approximately 14 m³/d, and the average drainage flow was 28 m³/d, resulting in a hydraulic retention time (HRT) of 19 days in the entire treatment plant. It is therefore expected that the average inlet and outlet pollutant concentrations for the studied period of 71 days, which is about 3.5 times bigger than the HRT in the system, will be suitable for performing a credible mass flow analysis.

2.5. Analytical methods

2.5.1 Target PFAS analysis in wastewater and sludge

Target PFAS in leachate liquid samples and sludge were analysed following the method described in WP1 (reported in D1.1), which developed a cost-effective testing method for PFAS analysis in complex matrices. The test method was designed to be easily replicable and transferable to any testing laboratory operating in support of industrial operators. The developed procedure and the obtained performance ensure robustness, reliability, and fast turnaround time, with low material costs, high throughput (more than 20 samples per day) and meet the needs for continuous PFAS control and monitoring in complex matrices.

Samples are prepared using an appropriate sample preparation method (e.g., solvent dilution or extraction) to determinate 30 analytes of the perfluoroalkyl family of substances from environmental matrices of interest, liquid or solid. The laboratory set the LOQ values starting from lowest point on the calibration curve:

- 10 µg/kg on the sludge matrix;
- 1 µg/L on the leachate and concentrate matrices;
- 0.02 µg/L on the wastewater and permeate matrix, deemed free of concentrated interfering substances.

For C6O4 (next generation flour-surfactant) the LOQ was:

- 50 µg/kg on the sludge matrix.
- 5µg/L on the leachate and concentrate matrices.
- 0.08 µg/L on the wastewater and permeate matrix, deemed free of concentrated interfering substances.

Table 5: Overview of analyzed PFAS and LOQs in different matrices.

30 target PFAS	PFDA, PFHpA, PFHxS, PFNA, PFOA, PFOS, PFDoDA, PFDoDS, PFDS, PFHpS, PFHxA, PFPeA, PFTTrDA, PFTeDA, PFUnDA, PFBA, PFBS, 4:2 FTSA, 6:2 FTSA, 8:2 FTSA, NADONA, EtFOSAA, PFOSA, MeFOSAA, PFNS, PFPeS, PFTTrDS, PFUnDS, HFPO-DA (= GenX), C6O4*
LOQ leachate and concentrate	1 µg/L
LOQ wastewater liquid	20 ng/L
LOQ solids	10 µg/kg

*50 µg/kg on the sludge matrix, 5µg/L on the leachate and concentrate matrices. 0.08 µg/L on the washing water

For chemical and biological sludge, it was decided to apply a solid-liquid extraction procedure to extract PFAS from the solid matrix, using 10 mL of Methanol and sonicating at room temperature for 30 minutes. The samples are then centrifuged to separate the suspended solids from the liquid phase. After that the extraction solvent is ready for instrumental analysis. The extract from the solid is

concentrated to 1 mL and an Extracted Internal Standard (EIS) is added to monitor the analytical process.

For leachates and concentrates, an aliquot of the sample is diluted at least 10 times in methanol before separating the suspended solids from the liquid phase by centrifugation, to avoid that the PFAS bind to the inner surface of the sample container. At this point the sample can be prepared for the instrumental analysis. The method recommends a limit of 50 mg of solids in the total sample volume that is processed by dilution (this corresponds at 0.5% TSS in the matrix).

Permeate and washing waters are prepared directly in the glass sample container and then transferred into a vial, ready to be analyzed, in order not to lose PFAS adhering to the container wall.

All sample concentrations are determined by isotope dilution, according to the project-specific requirements, using isotopically labeled compounds added to the samples before injection. All the solutions prepared during the analysis must necessarily contain at least 30% of methanol to keep filming process on the walls of the containers under control. Analysis is conducted by LC-MS/MS in the multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) and negative ionization mode.

Target compounds are qualitatively identified in samples by comparing retention times (RTs) to RTs of isotopically labeled surrogates in the same samples or to RTs of target analytes in standards, where applicable, and by comparing product ion ratios to those in standards development. Qualitatively identified target compounds are then quantified based on their primary product ion responses.

Possible interference can be caused by the matrix, solvents, reagents, analytical standards and by glassware contamination. Method blanks (MB) and reagent blanks (RB) are prepared and analyzed with all samples and are used to demonstrate that laboratory supplies, preparation, and analysis steps, do not introduce interferences or PFAS artifacts at levels that would prevent the proper identification and integration of target analytes or bias quantitation, especially near the limit of quantitation (LOQ) or any project-specific concentration levels of interest. Careful selection of reagents and consumables is necessary because even low levels of PFAS contamination may alter the precision and bias of the method; background introduced by these materials (and variability thereof) is cumulative.

2.5.2 Analysis of conventional parameters of wastewaters and sludges

Also, conventional parameters to characterize the wastewaters, leachate and sludge were determined according to standard methods (APAH, 2012). The parameters pH, electrical conductivity, chemical oxygen demand (COD), biological oxygen demand (BOD5), total suspended solids (TSS), total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN), ammonia nitrogen ($\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$), nitrate nitrogen ($\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$), nitrite nitrogen ($\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$), and total phosphorous (TP), were analyzed in liquid samples.

Chloride (Cl^-), orthophosphate (P-PO_4), sulfate (SO_4^{2-}), sodium (Na^+), potassium (K^+), magnesium (Mg^{2+}), calcium (Ca^{2+}), $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ and $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ were measured by ion chromatography after filtration at $0.45\ \mu\text{m}$ (Whatman glass membrane filters). The content of total solids (TS%) and total volatile solids (TVS/TS%) were determined for the solid samples.

2.5.3 Analysis of Total Fluorine (TF)

Total fluorine (TF) was monitored in the sampling campaigns accomplished in Bugaria. For those analyses, all chemicals used were of analytical purity grade, unless specific purity is given. The following chemicals were used: deionized water (MilliQ), perchloric acid (HClO_4 , 70%, Fisher Chemicals, Waltham, MA, USA, Trace Metal Grade), heptane (HPLC grade, 99%, Fisher Chemicals),

acetonitrile (for gas chromatography MS, Supelco), diethyl ether (Fisher Chemicals), sodium fluoride (NaF, Chem-Lab, 98.5%), triphenylsilanol (TPSiOH, ThermoFisher scientific, 98%), fluorotriphenylsilane (TPSiF, 99%, Fluorochem), perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA, 96%, ThermoFisher scientific), perfluorodecanoic acid (PFDA, 97%, ThermoFisher scientific) and sodium biphenyl (SBP, ThermoFisher scientific, 15-25% w/w solution in diethylene glycol diethyl ether).

The instrumentation used was: vortex, rotator, gas chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (GC-MS/MS).

To optimize a method for TF determination, a method described in Koc et al. (2011) was used. The method involves two main steps:

- 1) Defluorination of PFOA by sodium biphenyl (SBS);
- 2) Derivatization of fluoride to volatile TPSiF (Triphenyl(4-(9-phenyl-9H-fluoren-9-yl)phenyl)silane).

GS-MS method optimisation and the procedures for defluorination are explained in Annexes 1 and 2.

Determination of TF in leachate samples

The sample preparation procedure was applied for the determination of TF in leachate samples.

The described procedure was applied to the determination of TF in leachate samples. Twice larger volumes were used: 12 ml of leachate sample was mixed with 3 mL SBP in a 50 mL polypropylene test tube to conduct defluorination for 2 hours by shaking. The organic and aqueous layers were separated by centrifugation for 10 min at 3600 rpm. Afterwards the aqueous phase was decanted and transferred in a 50 mL polypropylene test tube and washed with 3 ml diethyl ether. The aqueous phase was decanted again and 12 mL 36 μ M TPSiOH, 6 ml conc. HClO₄ and 3 mL heptane were added. The closed vessels were vigorously agitated using a vortex for approximately 2 hours at room temperature. An aliquot of the heptane layer was decanted and analysed by GC-MS.

3. Results

3.1. Mass flow analysis of PFAS at the Italian study sites

3.1.1 Mass flow analysis of PFAS at leachate treatment plant N°1

Concentrations of detected PFAS and solid content expressed as TS% for all collected samples at LTP N°1 as well as the flows at the sampling points are shown in Table 6. Results are expressed as average and standard deviations of data obtained during the different sampling events. The average daily flow of LTP N°1 was about $170 \pm 65 \text{ m}^3/\text{d}$ throughout the monitoring period, with a production of dewatered sludge of around 1 ton per day. Most (96%) of the produced sludge is from the biological treatment, whereas only the 4% is chemical sludge produced by the clari-flocculation unit.

PFAS detected in both liquid and solid samples contain PFBA, PFPeA, PFHxA, PFBS, PFOA, PFDA, PFOS, N-MeFOSAA and N-EtFOSAA. The observed Σ PFAS concentrations range from $4 \mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ up to $15 \mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ for liquid matrixes, whereas a much higher variability was detected in solid matrixes with Σ PFAS concentrations varying between $10 \text{ ug}/\text{kg}$ to $160 \text{ ug}/\text{kg}$. The PFAS were measured in both liquid and solid phases for the influent leachate sample due to the high TS% content of this sample (Table 7) and to get information on the partitioning of PFAS compounds between the liquid phase and the solid phase at the start of the leachate treatments train (see Figure 15 and Figure 16).

The most abundant PFAS in the liquid phase of influent samples were PFOA (30%), PFBS (27%) and PFBA (22%). In contrast, in the solid phase of the influent samples, the most abundant PFAS were PFBA (30%), PFOA (29%) and PFOS (16%). The precursors N-MeFOSAA and N-EtFOSAA were detected only in the solid matrix, whereas short-chain and long-chain PFAS were detected in both liquid and solid phases.

Figure 15: PFAS detected in the liquid phase of the influent leachate sample collected at LTP N°1

Figure 16: Partitioning of PFAS detected in the solid phase of the influent leachate sample collected at LTP N°1

In the dewatered sludge (solid phase), the predominant PFAS was PFOA (53%), followed by PFOS and PFBA. The solid matrix shows a higher content of long chain PFAS compared to short-chain compounds, probably due to the lower mobility of the long-chain compounds (Figure 17).

Figure 17: Partitioning of PFAS detected in the dewatered sludge – solid phase

In Table 7 typical characterization parameters for the liquid samples collected at LTP N°1 are summarized, whereas in Table 8 calculated PFAS mass flows for all the sampling points are shown. The LTP n°1 remove mainly COD, BOD5, N-NH4 and TSS to obtain concentrations below the legislative limits to be discharged into the WWTP.

Table 6: PFAS concentrations, flows and TS% measured at the different sampling points of LTP N°1 (average \pm standard deviations). Sampling point (SP) indications are referred to Figure 7

	Q (m ³ /d)	TS%	PFBA	PFPeA	PFHxA	PFBS	PFOA	PFDA	PFOS	N-MeFOSAA	N-EtFOSAA	Σ PFAS
Influent Leachate (SP1) ($\mu\text{g/L}$)			2.56 \pm 1.83	1.32 \pm 2.05	0.62 \pm 0.82	3.13 \pm 1.55	3.46 \pm 2.32	-	0.4 \pm 1.06	-	-	11.29 \pm 3.36
Solid phase of Influent leachate (SP1) ($\mu\text{g/kg}$)	170 \pm 65	0.39 \pm 0.20	23.72 \pm 26.93	3.03 \pm 8.03	1.73 \pm 4.59	7.08 \pm 12.86	22.26 \pm 16.35	1.45 \pm 3.83	12.07 \pm 11.73	3.04 \pm 5.19	3.47 \pm 5.95	77.85 \pm 77.72
Effluent Clari-flocculation (SP2) ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	169 \pm 65	0.85 \pm 0.67	2.82 \pm 1.78	1.3 \pm 1.92	0.89 \pm 0.62	3.14 \pm 1.68	5.38 \pm 5.95	-	0.83 \pm 1.66	-	0.14 \pm 0.38	14.51 \pm 9.53
Effluent Secondary Sedimentation (SP3) ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	167 \pm 47	0.82 \pm 0.42	3.54 \pm 1.49	2.27 \pm 3.16	1.39 \pm 0.33	3.58 \pm 1.16	3.75 \pm 1.79	-	-	-	-	12.45 \pm 6.72
Effluent UF (SP4) ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	177 \pm 46	-	3.55 \pm 1.05	2.07 \pm 2.9	1.22 \pm 0.64	3.65 \pm 1.05	2.57 \pm 0.9	-	-	-	-	13.05 \pm 3.89
Chemical Sludge (SP5) ($\mu\text{g/kg}$)	1 \pm 4	0.75 \pm 0.43	-	-	-	1.71 \pm 4.54	14.34 \pm 7.6	-	13.59 \pm 10.99	2.86 \pm 4.91	5.14 \pm 6.64	37.64 \pm 25.89
Waste Sludge (SP6) ($\mu\text{g/kg}$)	22 \pm 26	0.71 \pm 0.29	4.73 \pm 8.48	1.88 \pm 4.97	1.45 \pm 3.83	7.89 \pm 8.41	32.66 \pm 17.68	4.88 \pm 6.09	21.04 \pm 9.75	-	7.61 \pm 5.29	82.14 \pm 45.97
Dewatered Sludge (SP7) ($\mu\text{g/kg}$)	0.89 \pm 1.11	24.5 \pm 2.3	8.94 \pm 21.89	-	-	1.67 \pm 4.08	29.86 \pm 23.73	-	13 \pm 14.53	-	3.17 \pm 4.92	56.63 \pm 40.15
Supernatant (SP8) ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	22 \pm 26	-	2.8 \pm 1.21	0.88 \pm 2.16	0.92 \pm 0.46	2.74 \pm 0.82	2.84 \pm 0.95	-	-	-	-	10.17 \pm 3.04

Table 7: Conventional parameters of the liquid samples collected at LTP N°1 (average \pm standard deviations)

	Unit	Influent Leachate SP1	Effluent Clari-flocculation SP2	Effluent Secondary Sedimentation SP3	Effluent UF SP4	Supernatant SP8
pH	-	7.1 \pm 0.9	7.8 \pm 0.1	7.7 \pm 0.2	7.7 \pm 0.3	7.9 \pm 0.1
Conductivity	uS/cm	6404 \pm 2105	6846 \pm 1319	4594 \pm 877	4766 \pm 278	3953 \pm 669
TSS	mg/l	14217 \pm 28231	4908 \pm 9158	14795 \pm 14814	26 \pm 9	152 \pm 109
COD	mg/l	10532 \pm 16277	6226 \pm 9730	10813 \pm 8194	757 \pm 173	896 \pm 539
BOD5	mg/l	652 \pm 95	642 \pm 571	689 \pm 278	0 \pm 0	-
TKN	mg/l	1213 \pm 320	719 \pm 353	712 \pm 604	40 \pm 16	30 \pm 1
N-NH4	mg/l	601 \pm 186	582 \pm 107	13 \pm 12	15 \pm 7	25 \pm 1
Ptot	mg/l	24 \pm 14	51 \pm 86	154 \pm 77	4 \pm 4	4 \pm 3
Cl	mg/l	1191 \pm 719	902 \pm 245	784 \pm 150	979 \pm 65	878 \pm 125
NO2	mg/l	1 \pm 1	1 \pm 2	4 \pm 3	33 \pm 29	23 \pm 30
NO3	mg/l	13 \pm 19	15 \pm 12	311 \pm 252	451 \pm 145	502 \pm 5
P-PO4	mg/l	23 \pm 24	6 \pm 6	3 \pm 3	4 \pm 3	3 \pm 4
SO4	mg/l	187 \pm 148	122 \pm 83	129 \pm 88	210 \pm 23	247 \pm 91
Na	mg/l	781 \pm 217	809 \pm 96	866 \pm 91	960 \pm 71	783 \pm 98
K	mg/l	239 \pm 53	268 \pm 22	307 \pm 33	335 \pm 19	279 \pm 32
Mg	mg/l	105 \pm 29	98 \pm 23	88 \pm 10	93 \pm 11	84 \pm 13
Ca	mg/l	247 \pm 129	233 \pm 146	189 \pm 72	205 \pm 72	167 \pm 58

Table 8: PFAS mass flows for the selected sampling points at LTP N°1 (average \pm standard deviations). Sampling point (SP) indications are referred to Figure

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	PFBA (g/d)	PFPeA (g/d)	PFHxA (g/d)	PFBS (g/d)	PFOA (g/d)	PFDA (g/d)	PFOS (g/d)	N-MeFOSAA (g/d)	N-EtFOSAA (g/d)	Σ PFAS (g/d)
Influent Leachate (SP1)	0.58 \pm 0.42	0.20 \pm 0.34	0.13 \pm 0.18	0.70 \pm 0.39	0.86 \pm 0.72	-	0.12 \pm 0.30	0.0011 \pm 0.0021	0.0016 \pm 0.0028	2.60 \pm 1.01
Effluent Chiariflocculation (SP2)	0.62 \pm 0.39	0.24 \pm 0.34	0.19 \pm 0.14	0.70 \pm 0.42	1.36 \pm 1.66	-	0.24 \pm 0.45	0.0024 \pm 0.0044	0.04 \pm 0.11	3.40 \pm 2.74
Influent Biological reactor (calculated considering SP2 and SP8)	0.63 \pm 0.4	0.26 \pm 0.38	0.19 \pm 0.14	0.70 \pm 0.32	1.34 \pm 1.53	-	0.24 \pm 0.42	0.0023 \pm 0.0042	0.04 \pm 0.1	3.42 \pm 2.46
Effluent Secondary Sedimentation (SP3)	0.61 \pm 0.25	0.43 \pm 0.6	0.26 \pm 0.1	0.64 \pm 0.13	0.6 \pm 0.16	0.01 \pm 0.01	0.03 \pm 0.03	-	0.02 \pm 0.01	2.61 \pm 0.68
Effluent UF (SP4)	0.71 \pm 0.19	0.39 \pm 0.51	0.24 \pm 0.13	0.72 \pm 0.13	0.52 \pm 0.2	-	-	-	-	2.58 \pm 0.55
Chemical Sludge (SP5)	0.004 \pm 0.01	-	0.003 \pm 0.01	0.016 \pm 0.042	0.012 \pm 0.031	-	-	-	-	0.03 \pm 0.09
Waste Sludge (SP6)	0.08 \pm 0.09	0.04 \pm 0.08	0.03 \pm 0.03	0.10 \pm 0.12	0.10 \pm 0.11	-	0.01 \pm 0.01	-	-	0.36 \pm 0.34
Dewatered Sludge (SP7)	0.003 \pm 0.01	-	-	-	0.02 \pm 0.02	-	0.01 \pm 0.01	-	-	0.03 \pm 0.04
Supernatant (SP8)	0.1 \pm 0.08	0.02 \pm 0.05	0.03 \pm 0.04	0.11 \pm 0.10	0.11 \pm 0.11	-	-	-	-	0.37 \pm 0.28

Figure 18 illustrates the mass flow analysis (average data) for all the monitored PFAS compounds within the whole conventional LTP N°1. Considering the average mass flow, Figure 18 shows that 2.6 g/d of Σ PFAS is entering the LTP. Most of PFAS stays in the liquid phase and is transferred to the municipal WWTP, whereas only few grams of PFAS is adsorbed onto the dewatered sludge. Compared to the LTP influent, higher loads of short-chain PFAS (e.g., PFBA) can be measured at the LTP effluent, whereas only long-chain PFAS (i.e., PFOA, PFOS) and precursors are adsorbed onto the sludge.

In terms of Σ PFAS mass flow, there is a good agreement between PFAS entering the plant and PFAS exiting the plant. However, the same statement is not true when considering single compounds. Transformation of precursors and degradation processes are the probable reasons of this observed discrepancy.

Figure 18: PFAS mass flow analysis at LTP N°1

Figure 19 shows the mass flows of the different PFAS compounds at the influent and the effluent of LTP N°1. The long-chain PFAS, such as PFOA and PFOS, were more abundant in the influent, but have lower loads in the effluent. However, the presence of short-chain PFAS, such as PFBA, PFPeA, and PFHxA, increased throughout the biological treatment, probably because of degradation of some precursors as suggested in the literature (Yan et al., 2015). Although the PFDA, PFOS, N-MeFOSAA, and N-EtFOSAA were present in the influent in few grams, they were not found in the effluent sample.

Figure 19: PFAS mass flow in the influent (Sampling point N.1) and effluent (Sampling Point N.4) of LTP1

3.1.2 Mass flow analysis of PFAS at leachate treatment plant N°2

In Table 9 are reported concentrations of detected PFAS, and solid content expressed as TS% for all collected samples at LTP N°2. Results are expressed as average and standard deviations of data obtained during different sampling events. Furthermore, in the same table are reported measured flowrate at the corresponding sampling points (SP). As discussed in the previous section, at LTP 2 produced sewage sludge is treated together with municipal sludge. The average daily flow rates of LTP2 and of the connected WWTP are $339 \pm 175 \text{ m}^3/\text{d}$ and $2407 \pm 383 \text{ m}^3/\text{d}$, respectively. The production of the dewatered sludge is about 2.5 ton/d.

PFAS detected in both liquid and solid samples included PFBA, PFBS, PFHpA, PFPeA, PFOA, PFOS, PFHxA, and 6:2 FTSA. In the influent leachate to the plant were detected only the short-chain compounds PFBA, PFBS and PFHxA, which are the same compounds detected in the final effluent of the LTP 2 (Table 9). On the contrary, detected PFAS in the biological sludge of LTP 2 included the short-chain PFBA and the long-chain PFOA and PFOS.

During the different collection events, PFBA, PFBS, PFPeA and PFHxA were detected in the influent of the municipal WWTP, whereas PFBA, PFBS, PFHpA, PFPeA, PFOA, PFHxA, and 6:2 FTSA were found in the final effluent. Compounds that were detected in the effluent but were not present in the influent may be produced due to precursors degradations. In the dewatered sludge of the municipal WWTP, no PFAS compounds were measured above the analytical LOQ. As described above, biological sludge produced during landfill leachate treatment is treated together with municipal sludge. Probably, PFAS detected in sludge from LTP 2 was diluted after mixing with the sludge of the municipal WWTP and became non detectable by analytical instruments. Overall, PFBA was the most abundant PFAS compound detected in all the different matrices, as shown by Figure 20 and Figure 21.

Figure 20: PFAS partitioning for the effluent and waste sludge from leachate line

Figure 21: PFAS detected in the liquid phase of the influent and effluent of the WWTP

In Table 10 are reported typical characterization parameters for the liquid samples collected at LTP N°2. On the contrary, in Table 11 are reported PFAS mass flow data calculated for all the sampling points. The LTP n°2 was able to reduce the COD, BOD5, TSS, TN and TP in order to meet the effluent limit standards for the discharge into the municipal WWTP.

Table 9: PFAS concentrations, Flow rates and TS% measured at the different sampling points of LTP N°2 (average \pm standard deviations). Sampling point (SP) indications are referred to Figure 8

	Q (m ³ /d)	TS%	PFBA	PFBS	PFHpA	PFPeA	PFOA	PFOS	PFHxA	6:2 FTSA	Σ PFAS
Influent Leachate (SP1) ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	339 \pm 175	3.5%	5.68 \pm 3.89	2.58 \pm 4.33	-	-	-	-	1.25 \pm 2.50	<	9.50 \pm 10.19
Effluent Leachate (SP2) ($\mu\text{g/kg}$)	206 \pm 131	-	0.83 \pm 0.57	0.25 \pm 0.5	-	-	-	-	0.5 \pm 0.58	-	1.58 \pm 0.96
Influent WWTP (SP3) ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	2407 \pm 383	-	0.36 \pm 0.34	0.23 \pm 0.0	-	0.07 \pm 0.09	-	-	0.01 \pm 0.02	-	0.67 \pm 0.45
Effluent WWTP (SP4) ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	2298 \pm 411	-	0.36 \pm 0.02	0.18 \pm 0.02	0.02 \pm 0.0	0.07 \pm 0.01	0.09 \pm 0.0	-	0.18 \pm 0.01	0.01 \pm 0.02	0.91 \pm 0.01
Solid phase of Waste sludge leachate (SP5) ($\mu\text{g/kg}$)	162 \pm 104	1.7	8.25 \pm 16.5	-	-	<	2.75 \pm 5.5	2.75 \pm 5.5	-	-	13.75 \pm 16.5
Liquid phase of Waste sludge leachate (SP5) ($\mu\text{g/L}$)		Liquid	0.83 \pm 0.57	0.25 \pm 0.5	-	-	-	-	0.5 \pm 0.58	-	1.58 \pm 0.96
Waste sludge WWTP (SP6) ($\mu\text{g/kg}$)	109 \pm 114	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Supernatant (SP7A) ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	108 \pm 61	-	0.55 \pm 0.64	0.25 \pm 0.5	-	-	-	-	0.25 \pm 0.5	-	1.05 \pm 0.1
Supernatant (SP7B) ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	150 \pm 84	-	0.58 \pm 0.68	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.58 \pm 0.68
Dewatered sludge (SP8) ($\mu\text{g/kg}$)	2.2 \pm 1.2	25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 10: Conventional parameters of the liquid samples collected at LTP N°2 (average \pm standard deviations)

	Unit	Influent Leachate (SP 1)	Effluent Leachate (SP 2)	Influent WWTP (SP 3)	Effluent WWTP (SP 4)	Supernatant (SP 7A)	Supernatant (SP 7B)
COD	mg/l	5670 \pm 1060	370 \pm 195	328 \pm 100	36 \pm 21	1108 \pm 205	1171 \pm 520
BOD5	mg/l	1160	0	73	0	138	141
TSS	mg/l	3560 \pm 3275	63 \pm 41	126 \pm 3	6.5 \pm 6.4	810 \pm 416	168 \pm 23
pH	-	7.1 \pm 0.5	7.7 \pm 0.3	7 \pm 0.2	7.5 \pm 0.3	7.2 \pm 0.1	6.9 \pm 0.2
Conductivity	μ S/cm	5938 \pm 3608	2234 \pm 562	824 \pm 255	1011 \pm 150	2623 \pm 598	2643 \pm 388
TKN	mg/l	769 \pm 316	99 \pm 86	46 \pm 15	7.3 \pm 1.2	347 \pm 25	294 \pm 52
NH4	mg/l	399 \pm 262	22 \pm 17	28 \pm 11	0.9 \pm 0.9	80 \pm 22	93 \pm 23
Cl	mg/l	650 \pm 393	369 \pm 21	78 \pm 19	146 \pm 29	350 \pm 47	346 \pm 39
NO2	mg/l	0.7 \pm 0.4	36 \pm 60	0.6 \pm 0.6	2.3 \pm 2.7	0.4 \pm 0.5	0.7 \pm 0.5
NO3	mg/l	2.7 \pm 1.9	4.7 \pm 4.5	2 \pm 1.1	15 \pm 7	3.7 \pm 2.7	2.9 \pm 1.1
PO4	mg/l	25 \pm 17	2 \pm 2	11 \pm 4	4 \pm 4	67 \pm 14	78 \pm 40
SO4	mg/l	90 \pm 131	120 \pm 65	65 \pm 26	83 \pm 24	216 \pm 242	39 \pm 7

Table 11: PFAS Mass flow data for the selected sampling point at LTP N°2 (average \pm standard deviations). Sampling point (SP) indications are referred to Figure 8

	PFBA (g/d)	PFBS (g/d)	PFHpA (g/d)	PFPeA (g/d)	PFOA (g/d)	PFOS (g/d)	PFHxA (g/d)	6:2 FTSA (g/d)	Σ PFAS (g/d)
Influent Leachate (SP1)	2.49 \pm 1.328	0.996 \pm 1.633	-	-	-	-	0.474 \pm 0.948	-	3.959 \pm 3.654
Effluent Leachate (SP2)	0.277 \pm 0.206	0.099 \pm 0.197	-	-	-	-	0.147 \pm 0.188	-	0.522 \pm 0.455
Influent WWTP (SP3)	0.762 \pm 0.554	0.602 \pm 0.225	-	0.126 \pm 0.178	-	-	0.028 \pm 0.039	-	1.518 \pm 0.546
Effluent WWTP (SP4)	0.883 \pm 0.293	0.454 \pm 0.184	0.051 \pm 0.017	0.158 \pm 0.024	0.21 \pm 0.07	-	0.426 \pm 0.101	0.026 \pm 0.037	2.207 \pm 0.652
Waste sludge leachate (SP5)	0.195 \pm 0.159	0.06 \pm 0.119	-	-	0.011 \pm 0.022	0.011 \pm 0.022	0.106 \pm 0.124	-	0.382 \pm 0.326
Waste sludge WWTP (SP6)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Supernatant (SP7A)	0.127 \pm 0.173	0 \pm 0	0.127 \pm 0.173						
Supernatant (SP7B)	0.124 \pm 0.144	0 \pm 0	0.124 \pm 0.144						
Dewatered sludge (SP8)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Figure 22 and Figure 23 show the PFAS mass flow analysis for LTP 2 and for the municipal WWTP, respectively. In the case of LTP2, an important mass load of PFAS compounds is transferred to the municipal WWTP through the effluent to the water treatment line and by the waste sludge to the sludge treatment line. In both water and sludge treatment lines, existing biological processes can influence PFAS presence in the liquid phase by biological transformation of precursors and by adsorption processes. Furthermore, the water and sludge treatment lines are connected to each other by the recirculation of the supernatant. However, in the supernatant only PFBA at a relatively low concentration was detected (Table 11).

As observed for LTP1, a closure of mass balance for each PFAS compound is not possible by the obtained data. Even in this case, biological transformation of precursors or other degradation effects are the probable reasons of the discrepancy between the PFAS mass loads entering and exiting the plant.

Considering the PFAS mass flow through the municipal WWTP, there is a much better consistency of results between the load of PFAS entering the WWTP and the mass of PFAS exiting the plant. This can be observed for single PFAS compounds as well as for Σ PFAS (30) (Figure 18). Presence of a higher number of PFAS compounds in the effluent compared to the influent is probably related to precursors degradation during biological treatment. Although, PFAS were detected in the solid phase of the waste sludge produced at the LTP2, no PFAS could be measured in the dewatered sludge of the municipal WWTP (Table 9). Probably, PFAS were diluted after mixing the sludge from the LTP with the municipal sludge, and the analytical instruments that used a LOQ of 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ were not able to detect PFAS in this solid matrix.

Figure 22: PFAS Mass flow analysis at LTP N°2

Figure 23: PFAS mass flow analysis at the municipal WWTP

3.1.3 Mass flow analysis of PFAS at leachate treatment plant N°3

As previously described, LTP N°3 uses advanced treatment technologies for leachate treatment compared to LTP N°1 and LTP N°2, which can be classified as conventional leachate treatment plants. LTP 3 includes a leachate treatment line and a concentrate treatment line with chemical and physical units. The daily flow rate of LTP N°3 is around 1560 m³/d with a production of chemical solids/sludge of around 11 tons per day.

The PFAS detected in the collected samples included PFBA, PFPeA, PFHxA, PFBS, PFHpA, PFOA, PFDA, PFNA, 8:2 FTSA, PFOS, N-MeFOSAA, and N-EtFOSAA. Particularly, PFDA, PFNA, 8:2 FTSA, PFOS, N-MeFOSAA and N-EtFOSAA were present only in the vacuum filtration solids, whereas they were absent in the liquid samples. Probably, these compounds were only present in the solid phase of the influent leachate, which was characterized by a low concentration of suspended solids (Table 13) compared to LTP1 and LTP2 and that were removed during the different filtration steps before RO. In addition, PFAS concentration in the vacuum filtration solid (368 ± 296 ug/kg as ΣPFAS) was much higher than in the dewatered sludge (38 ± 6 ug/kg as ΣPFAS) resulting from the chemical treatment of the RO concentrate.

The ΣPFAS (30) concentrations ranged from 8 µg/L to 10 µg/L in the influent leachate matrix during the different sampling events. In contrast, PFAS level in the ROx concentrate was five times higher. It can be estimated to have a concentration factor (CF) of 5 during the full RO process.

Both the influent leachate (SP1) and the treated concentrate (SP7) have a high presence of PFOA, PFBS and PFBA, as shown in Figure 19. In the solids retained from the vacuum filtration, PFOA and PFOS are the most relevant compounds with a share of 32% and 25%, respectively. Finally, PFOA (47%) and PFBS (40%) were the most abundant PFAS in the chemical sludge (Figure 25).

Figure 24: Share of PFAS detected in the influent leachate and in the treated ROx concentrate at LTP N°3 – liquid phase

Figure 25: Share of PFAS detected in the solids from vacuum filtration and in the dewatered sludge at LTP N°3 – solid phase

In Table 13 are reported typical characterization parameters for the liquid samples collected at LTP N°1. On the contrary, in Table 14 are reported PFAS mass flow data calculated for all the sampling points. The LTP n°3 during the sampling campaign was able to remove macro-pollutants from landfill leachate, such COD, BOD5, TN, TP and TSS, to reach legislative limits for the discharge into the municipal sewage system. The pH was lowered below 4 before UF to avoid the scaling of RO membrane while it was increased above 10 in the concentrate line in order to strip the ammonia.

Table 12: PFAS concentrations, Flow rates and TS% measured at the different sampling points of LTP N°3 (average ± standard deviations). Sampling point (SP) indications are referred to Figure 9

	Q (m3/d)	TS%	PFBA	PFPeA	PFHxA	PFBS	PFHpA	PFOA	PFDA	PFNA	8:2 FTSA	PFOS	N- MeFOSAA	N- EtFOSAA	ΣPFAS
Influent															
Leachate (SP1) (µg/L)	1560	-	1.64 ± 0.41	-	0.33 ± 0.58	2.24 ± 0.35	-	4.76 ± 0.59	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.98 ± 0.71
Vacuum Filtration Solids (SP2) (µg/kg)	7	43	-	-	-	-	-	115.5 ± 71.4	6 ± 8.5	6 ± 8.5	23.5 ± 17.7	93 ± 80.6	71 ± 60.8	52.5 ± 48.8	367.5 ± 296.3
Permeate UF (SP3) (µg/L)	1555	-	2.25 ± 0.07	-	-	2.1 ± 0	-	3.95 ± 0.21	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.3 ± 0.14
Permeate RO (SP4) (µg/L)	1340	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Concentrate ROx (SP5) (µg/L)	215	-	19.95 ± 10.4	-	4.98 ± 1.3	17.08 ± 0.04	1.56 ± 0.2	18.21 ± 5.51	-	-	-	-	-	-	61.77 ± 17.44
Concentrate before stripping (SP6) (µg/L)	213	-	9.15 ± 12.94	1.06 ± 0.06	3.43 ± 0.39	12.24 ± 0.8	1.16 ± 0.08	15.13 ± 6.18	-	-	-	-	-	-	42.16 ± 20.28
Treated Concentrate (SP7) (µg/L)	213	-	11 ± 5.66	1 ± 1.41	3.42 ± 0.82	14.15 ± 2.06	1.31 ± 0.13	19.18 ± 2.29	-	-	-	-	-	-	50.06 ± 12.37
Dewatered Sludge (SP8) (ug/kg)	4	39	5 ± 7.1	-	-	15 ± 2.8	-	17.5 ± 3.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	37.5 ± 6.4

Table 13: Conventional parameters of liquid samples from LTP N°3 (average \pm standard deviations)

	Unit	Influent Leachate SP1	Permeate UF SP3	Permeate RO SP4	Concentrate ROx SP5	Concentrate before stripping SP6	Treated Concentrate SP7
pH	-	8.3 \pm 0	2.5 \pm 0.3	3.5 \pm 0.2	1.8 \pm 0.2	11.46	11.2 \pm 0.5
Conductivity	uS/cm	6700 \pm 2517	5411 \pm 7649	126 \pm 78	73500 \pm 38891	14900	18720 \pm 6053
TSS	mg/l	76 \pm 6	0 \pm 0	0 \pm 0	0 \pm 0	40	35 \pm 35
COD	mg/l	532 \pm 95	96 \pm 96	18 \pm 14	2978 \pm 2813	934	1573 \pm 908
TKN	mg/l	423 \pm 66	375 \pm 138	3 \pm 3	3685 \pm 2515	1820	131 \pm 36
NH4	mg/l	414 \pm 58	340 \pm 115	1 \pm 0	3444 \pm 2183	1802	82 \pm 66
Ptot	mg/l	2 \pm 0	2 \pm 1	0 \pm 0	21 \pm 4	1.3	0 \pm 0
Cl	mg/l	576 \pm 71	972 \pm 139	16 \pm 12	8136 \pm 2421	7614	6298 \pm 1496
NO2	mg/l	0 \pm 1	0 \pm 0	0 \pm 0	0 \pm 0	0	0 \pm 0
NO3	mg/l	4 \pm 5	3 \pm 4	0 \pm 0	14 \pm 20	11.7	15 \pm 21
P-PO4	mg/l	1 \pm 0	1 \pm 1	0 \pm 0	8 \pm 4	0	0 \pm 0
SO4	mg/l	187 \pm 101	1864 \pm 965	7 \pm 8	25274 \pm 4079	6045	6266 \pm 803
Na	mg/l	518 \pm 102	477 \pm 103	3 \pm 4	4564 \pm 2749	2660	3177 \pm 675
K	mg/l	203 \pm 45	181 \pm 35	1 \pm 2	1622 \pm 920	892	1148 \pm 269
Mg	mg/l	163 \pm 15	78 \pm 22	0 \pm 0	839 \pm 410	0	0 \pm 0
Ca	mg/l	165 \pm 20	84 \pm 12	1 \pm 1	433 \pm 114	4439	3862 \pm 1682

Table 14: PFAS Mass flow data for the selected sampling point at LTP N°3 (average ± standard deviations). Sampling point (SP) indications are referred to Figure 9

	PFBA (g/d)	PFPeA (g/d)	PFHxA (g/d)	PFBS (g/d)	PFHpA (g/d)	PFOA (g/d)	PFNA (g/d)	8:2 FTSA (g/d)	PFDA (g/d)	PFOS (g/d)	N-MeFOSAA (g/d)	N-EtFOSAA (g/d)	ΣPFAS (g/d)
Influent Leachate (SP1)	2.56 ± 0.64	<	0.52 ± 0.9	3.5 ± 0.55	<	7.43 ± 0.92	<	<	<	<	<	<	14 ± 1.11
Vacuum Filtration (SP2)	<	<	<	<	<	0.28 ± 0.17	0.01 ± 0.02	0.01 ± 0.02	0.06 ± 0.04	0.23 ± 0.2	0.17 ± 0.15	0.13 ± 0.12	0.89 ± 0.72
Permeate UF (SP3)	3.5 ± 0.11	<	<	3.26 ± 0.0	<	6.14 ± 0.33	<	<	<	<	<	<	12.9 ± 0.22
Permeate RO (SP4)	<	<	<	<	<	-	<	<	<	<	<	<	<
Concentrate ROx (SP5)	4.19 ± 2.18	<	1.05 ± 0.27	3.58 ± 0.01	0.33 ± 0.04	3.82 ± 1.16	<	<	<	<	<	<	12.96 ± 3.66
Concentrate before stripping (SP6)	1.9 ± 2.69	0.22 ± 0.01	0.71 ± 0.08	2.54 ± 0.17	0.24 ± 0.02	3.15 ± 1.28	<	<	<	<	<	<	8.76 ± 4.22
Treated Concentrate (SP 7)	2.29 ± 1.18	0.21 ± 0.29	0.71 ± 0.17	2.94 ± 0.43	0.27 ± 0.03	3.99 ± 0.48	<	<	<	<	<	<	10.41 ± 2.57
Dewatered Sludge (SP8)	0.01 ± 0.01	<	<	0.03 ± 0.0	<	0.03 ± 0.01	<	<	<	<	<	<	0.07 ± 0.0

The PFAS mass flow analysis for LTP N°3 is shown in Figure 26 and Figure 27 for the leachate treatment line and for the RO concentrate treatment line, respectively. The total PFAS mass flow at the influent to the leachate treatment line is about 14 ± 1.1 g/d, and it shows an important presence of PFOA, PFBS and PFBA. Solid samples collected from pretreatment units (i.e., flotation, sand filter and UF) contain a mass of 0.89 ± 0.72 g/d of PFAS compounds. On the other side, the RO permeate has PFAS concentrations below the LOQ, while the RO concentrate contains 13 ± 3.7 g/d as Σ PFAS (30). Therefore, most of the PFAS contained in the influent leachate are accumulated in the RO concentrate. However, treatment of RO concentrate by clari-flocculation process does not remove PFAS, which are discharged into the sewage system together with the RO permeate nullifying the good removal obtained by the RO process. The clari-flocculation process was designed to remove heavy metals and other conventional contaminants from the RO concentrate, and it was not implemented for PFAS removal, which represents a new challenge for the water treatment sector.

Figure 26: PFAS mass flow for the Leachate treatment line (LTP N°3)

Particularly, by analysing the PFAS mass flow in concentrate line treatment, only few grams per day of PFAS compounds are found in the chemical sludge from the physical chemical reactor, while almost all PFAS are found in the treated concentrate (10.4 ± 2.6 g/d as Σ PFAS), which is subsequently discharged into the sewage with the RO permeate.

Figure 27: PFAS mass flow for the concentrate treatment line (LTP N°3)

3.1.4 Mass Balances comparison between the investigated LTPs in Italy

In Table 15 is reported a comparison between the mass loads of PFAS compounds entering LTP1, LTP2 and LTP3. For all the three plants, short-chain PFAS were mainly detected in the liquid phases of the investigated streams, and particularly in the discharged effluents. On the contrary, long-chain PFAS and precursors were found in the analyzed solid matrices. Overall, the highest PFAS load was measured in the liquid phase for all the three investigated LTP.

PFBA and PFBS were compounds detected at high concentrations in all three landfill leachate matrices. High concentrations of PFOA were also measured at LTP1 and LTP3.

Table 15: Comparison of PFAS Mass Balances

	Leachate treatment LTP N°1				Leachate treatment LTP N°2				Leachate treatment LTP N°3					
	Influent Leach.	Effluent UF	Waste Sludge	Mass balance Error (%)	Influent Leach.	Effluent Leach.	Waste sludge leach.	Mass balance Error (%)	Influent Leach.	RO Perm.	Treated Conc.	Vacuum Filtrat.	Dew. Sludge	Mass bal. Error (%)
PFBA (g/d)	0.580 ± 0.422	0.713 ± 0.190	0.080 ± 0.090	-37%	2.490 ± 1.328	0.277 ± 0.206	0.195 ± 0.159	81%	2.558 ± 0.645	-	2.338 ± 1.202	-	0.009 ± 0.012	8%
PFPeA (g/d)	0.201 ± 0.344	0.387 ± 0.510	0.040 ± 0.080	-112%	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.213 ± 0.301	-	-	-
PFHxA (g/d)	0.134 ± 0.180	0.237 ± 0.132	0.030 ± 0.030	-99%	0.474 ± 0.948	0.147 ± 0.188	0.106 ± 0.124	47%	0.520 ± 0.901	-	0.727 ± 0.174	-	-	-
PFBS (g/d)	0.696 ± 0.393	0.716 ± 0.132	0.100 ± 0.120	-17%	0.996 ± 1.633	0.099 ± 0.197	0.060 ± 0.119	84%	3.500 ± 0.546	-	3.006 ± 0.437	-	0.029 ± 0.001	13%
PFHpA (g/d)	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.011 ± 0.022	-	-	-	0.278 ± 0.027	-	-	-
PFOA (g/d)	0.864 ± 0.725	0.523 ± 0.202	0.100 ± 0.110	28%	-	-	-	-	7.426 ± 0.924	-	4.077 ± 0.487	0.281 ± 0.174	0.035 ± 0.013	41%
PFNA (g/d)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.015 ± 0.021	-	-
8:2 FTSA (g/d)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.015 ± 0.021	-	-
PFDA (g/d)	0.001 ± 0.002	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.060 ± 0.040	-	-
PFOS (g/d)	0.119 ± 0.296	-	0.010 ± 0.010	92%	-	-	0.011 ± 0.022	-	-	-	-	0.226 ± 0.196	-	-
N-MeFOSAA (g/d)	0.0011 ± 0.0021	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.173 ± 0.148	-	-
N-EtFOSAA (g/d)	0.0016 ± 0.0028	-	0.000 ± 0.0026	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.128 ± 0.119	-	-
ΣPFAS (g/d)	2.597 ± 1.006	2.576 ± 0.555	0.360 ± 0.340	-13%	3.959 ± 3.654	0.522 ± 0.455	0.382 ± 0.326	77%	14.004 ± 1.111	-	10.639 ± 2.629	0.895 ± 0.721	0.072 ± 0.000	17%
Mass Balance Error for ΣPFAS (%)	-13%				77%				17%					

3.2. PFAS screening and mass flow analysis at the Bulgarian study sites

In the following paragraphs, the results of the sampling campaigns accomplished in Bulgaria are analysed and summarized. The detailed data can be found in the Annexes.

3.2.1 PFAS in the untreated leachate from ten landfills

In the untreated leachates of the 10 investigated landfills, only seven out of the 30 analysed PFAS (Table 5) were detected above the LOQ of 1 µg/L. These PFAS were PFBA, PFBS, PFHxA, PFPeA, PFOA, PFOS and 4:2 FTSA. The PFAS sums for each sampling campaign and for each landfill are depicted in Figure 28.

Figure 28: Sum of PFAS in the untreated leachate of 10 landfills

The total PFAS concentration in three landfills (Pleven, Vratsa and Zlatitsa) was lower than in the others. However, the total concentration of PFAS for each landfill varied between the two sampling campaigns. This suggests that more frequent sampling will be required to obtain credible values for each landfill.

There are no clear relationships between the detected concentration and the size or the age of the landfill. To illustrate, Burgas is the oldest landfill, and the leachate is recirculated continuously over the landfill cells. However, the total PFAS concentration is not the highest.

The concentrations of the four PFAS that occurred more frequently are shown in Figure 29.

Figure 29: Concentration of the four most frequently detected PFAS in the untreated leachate of the studied 10 landfills

Notes: PFBS detected in 12 samples, PFHxA detected in 14 samples, PFBA detected in 8 samples, PFPeA detected in 7 samples

The concentration of PFBS was found to be the highest, with values ranging from 1.5 to 8 µg/L. The average and median values were 3.9 µg/L and 3.5 µg/L, respectively. The concentration of PFHxA was found to be the second highest, with values ranging from 1.0 to 5 µg/L. The average and median values were 2.6 µg/L and 2.1 µg/L, respectively.

3.2.2 Correlation between PFAS (sum) and total fluorine at Sofia LTP1

Total fluorine was measured three times at all sampling points of the Sofia leachate treatment plant (in July, November and December 2023). Similar (increasing or decreasing) trends between sampling points are noticeable (Figure 30).

Figure 30: Correlation between PFAS (sum of all detected PFAS) and TF

Note: SP - sampling point

However, the ratio between TF and the sum of PFAS-F varies widely, as shown in Table 16. The concentration of fluorine bound in a specific PFAS (PFAS-F) was calculated based on the proportion of the molar masses of fluorine and the corresponding PFAS. These results indicate that further research is needed to enhance the analytical methods and check whether there is correlation between these two parameters.

Table 16: Ratio TF to Sum PFAS-F

	July	November	December
Sampling point 1	28	PFAS below LOQ	PFAS below LOQ
Sampling point 2	13	56	11
Sampling point 3	35	79	44
Sampling point 4	37	PFAS below LOQ	PFAS below LOQ
Sampling point 6	88	70	46
Sampling point 7	PFAS below LOQ	49	87

3.2.2 Mass flow analysis of PFAS at the LTP1 of Sofia

A total of 30 different PFAS were analyzed (Table 5). All data are provided in Annex 4.

Eight of the analysed PFAS were above the LOQ (different LOQs were used, see Annex 4). These are the same seven PFAS that were discussed in the previous section plus PFHpA, which was detected for Sofia only in the sampling campaigns in December and January (not included in the analysis of the 10 landfills).

Figure 31 displays the concentrations of the four most frequently occurring PFAS in the inlet of the treatment plant (sampling point 2).

Figure 31: Concentration of the four most frequently detected PFAS in the untreated leachate of Sofia landfill (sampling point 2)

Figure 32 displays the concentrations of the five most frequently occurring PFAS in the outlet of the treatment plant (sampling point 6).

Figure 32: Concentration of the five most frequently detected PFAS in the treated leachate of Sofia landfills (sampling point 6)

The concentrations of PFAS in the untreated and treated leachate had different LOQs (see Annex 4), which could be the reason for the detection of the long-chain PFOS in the effluent (sampling point 6) that was not detected in the influent (sampling point 2). However, this conclusion is uncertain because PFOS were detected at sampling point 3, which is the other inlet to the treatment plant. Nevertheless, it should be noted that sampling point 3 was also analyzed using the same LOQ of 0,02 µg/L as the effluent (sampling point 6).

A mass flow balance of the loads (L) was performed for the sum of the nine PFAS detected (Figure 22). The measured flow rates (Q) and concentrations (c) were averaged over the six sampling campaigns.

Figure 33: PFAS mass flow analysis at Sofia LTP1

The results show that the mass balance is incorrect:

1. the sum of the loads at points 2 and 3 is not equal to the loads at point 4 and
2. the sum of the loads at points 6 and 7 is not equal to the loads at point 4.

All samples were analysed for the chloride ion in order to verify the mass balance. The mass flow analysis for chloride is shown in Figure 34. Similar to the PFAS mass flow analysis, the measured flow rates and concentrations were averaged over the six sampling campaigns.

Figure 34: Chloride mass flow analysis at Sofia LTP1

The results indicate that the mass balance for chloride is accurate for points 2, 3, and 4, but inaccurate for the final effluent, specifically points 4, 6, and 7. After discussing with the plant authorities, it was revealed that the low concentrations of PFAS and chloride in the effluent originates in an additional flow between the LPT2 and the sampling point 6 in LPT1 (Figure 13). This flow is not depicted in the flow scheme. As no flow data of this additional flow is available, the mass flow cannot be recalculated.

A potential reason for the discrepancy in the results of the PFAS mass flow balance at sampling points 2, 3, and 4, in comparison to the accurate results for chloride, is that low concentrations of PFAS (in µg/L) are multiplied by high quantities (m³/d). Even a small error in the determination of the concentration can lead to a significant mistake. For instance, in the case of Sofia:

Table 17: Comparison of loads for PFAS and chlorides

Sampling point	Type of liquid	LOQ	Flowrate Q	Measured concentration PFAS	PFAS load	Measured concentration Chloride	Chloride load
		µg/L	m ³ /d	µg/L	mg/d	mg/l	kg/d
Sampling point 2	leachate	0,1 or 1	14,4	4,28	62	1854	26,7
Sampling point 3	drainage water	0,02	28	0,95	27	79	2,22
Verification ratio = Load in point 2/Load in point 3					approx. 2		approx. 12

The pollution load entering with the drainage water (point 3) for PFAS is only approximately half the pollution load entering with the leachate (point 2). In contrast, for chlorides, this ratio is approx. 12.

Using a lower LOQ results in the detection of more compounds, leading to a higher sum of PFAS. Figure 3 demonstrates that mass flow analysis for LTP2 should result in equal loads for flows 1 and 3. The mass flow analysis for PFAS and Cl in LTP2 is presented in Figure 35.

Figure 35: Mass flow balance for PFAS and Cl for LTP2 in Sofia based on average values

The comparison of mass flows between PFAS and chlorides reveals a significant discrepancy. This is likely due to the different water matrix dependent LOQs. This results in higher PFAS concentration in the less polluted flow 3 (Table 18).

Table 18: Comparison of flows in sampling points 1 and 3 in relation to LOQ used

LOQ µg/L		Sampling point 1	LOQ µg/L		Sampling point 3										
		30/10/2023	14/11/2023	29/11/23	11/12/23	28/12/23	09/01/24			30/10/2023	14/11/2023	29/11/23	11/12/23	28/12/23	09/01/24
0,1	4-2 FTS	<	<	<	<	not measured	<	0,02	4-2 FTS	<	<	<	<	<	<
1	PFBA	<	<	<	<	not measured	0,5	0,02	PFBA	0,09	0,03	0,08	0,09	0,07	0,08
0,1	PFBS	<	<	<	<	not measured	0,2	0,02	PFBS	0,56	0,16	0,53	0,55	0,45	0,40
0,1	PFHpA	<	<	<	<	not measured	0,1	0,02	PFHpA	0,03	<	0,03	0,03	0,02	0,03
1	PFHpS	<	<	<	<	not measured	<	0,02	PFHpS	<	<	<	<	<	<
1	PFHxA	<	<	<	<	not measured	0,3	0,02	PFHxA	0,16	0,05	0,14	0,16	0,12	0,13
1	PFOA	<	<	<	<	not measured	0,1	0,02	PFOA	0,03	<	0,03	0,04	0,02	0,02
0,1	PFOS	<	<	<	<	not measured	<	0,02	PFOS	0,06	0,03	0,06	0,06	0,05	0,04
1	PFPeA	<	<	<	<	not measured	0,2	0,02	PFPeA	0,25	0,08	0,24	0,27	0,20	0,23
SOMMA		< LOQ	< LOQ	< LOQ	< LOQ	0,0	1,4		SOMMA	1,18	0,35	1,11	1,20	0,93	0,93

A higher number of PFAS were identified in flow 3, where a lower LOQ was used in comparison with flow 1.

3.3. Comparison of results from Italian, Bulgarian and other studies

PFAS concentration in untreated leachate

Table 19 shows the average concentrations of PFAS detected in untreated leachates in Bulgaria and Italy, which are compared with two other studies.

Table 19: Comparison of PFAS in untreated leachate between Bulgarian and Italian studies (average values in µg/L)

PFAS name	Bulgarian study		Italian study		
	10 landfills	Sofia	Landfill 1	Landfill 2	Landfill 3
4:2 FTSA	0.2	0.2	<	<	<
PFBA	1.4	0.8	2.56	5.68	1.64
PFBS	3.9	1.5	3.13	2.58	2.24
PFHpA	<	0.1	<	<	<
PFHxA	2.6	1.3	0.62	1.25	0.33
PFOA	1.7	0.2	3.46	<	4.76
PFPeA	1.3	1.0	1.32	<	<
PFOS	1	<	0.4	<	<
Sum PFAS	12	5.1	11.29	9.50	8.98
Other studies*	From 0,005 to 18 in Europe µg/L (Wei et al., 2019) up to 540 µg/L in Michigan ((Helmer et al., 2022)				

*These values are taken from Table 1 of this deliverable

The results indicate that all data from Bulgaria and Italy fall within the reported range for Europe (Wei et al., 2019).

Mass flow balance

Mass flow balances in Bulgaria and Italy show some differences between the input and output loads (Table 20).

Table 20: Comparison of mass balance errors in Bulgarian and Italian studies

Item	Bulgarian study	Italian study		
	Sofia	Landfill 1	Landfill 2	Landfill 3
Mass Balance Error for Σ PFAS (%)	59% (biological stage) 71% (entire plant)	-13%	77%	17%

Several reasons for these discrepancies were discussed in the Italian and Bulgarian reports, including:

- the general management of the leachate treatment plants and the presence of large accumulation volumes;
- different LOQs for the chemical determination of PFAS at different stages of treatment;
- the very low concentrations (in µg/L) which, when multiplied by the daily flow rate to obtain the load, could lead to large errors.

The improvement of the analytical methods for PFAS determination is a research challenge, because the matrices are too complex to be able to lower the LOQs.

4. Conclusions

In this document occurrence and mass flow analyses for 30 target PFAS compounds were accomplished in different landfill leachate management plants in Italy and Bulgaria with the scope to identify the most critical pathways of PFAS contamination for the environment during landfill leachate treatment and management.

In Italy, three full-scale landfill leachate treatment plants (LTP) were investigated in three different regions of the country to evaluate the fate of PFAS during conventional and advanced leachate treatments.

Two of the selected LTP (LTP1 and LTP2) treated the influent leachate using conventional treatments, such as biological treatment, clari-flocculation and filtration by UF membrane. The third selected LTP3 treats landfill leachate by using an advanced treatment technology such as RO. The produced concentrate is then treated by clari-flocculation process and stripping. Sampling strategies were defined to take into account hydraulic retention times and sludge retention times of the plants to accomplish accurate mass flow analysis.

Results of the investigation showed that almost all the detected PFAS in the effluent remain in the liquid phase, which is then discharged into a municipal wastewater treatment plant. A small amount of PFAS, and particularly long chain-PFAS, is adsorbed onto the sludge. In addition, degradation of precursors can increase the concentration of target PFAS in the effluent. A similar discussion is valid for PFAS entering a municipal WWTP with biological and conventional treatments. Thus, PFAS compounds are eventually almost completely discharged into the receiving aquatic environment. This poses a serious threat for the feasibility of water reuse (e.g., agricultural irrigation, etc.) as well as for the environmental quality of the affected water bodies.

A much lower PFAS load was detected in the collected solid samples (i.e., chemical, and biological sludges), which are produced during leachate treatment. Furthermore, PFAS concentration was below the analytical LOQ in samples of the dewatered sludge collected at the investigated municipal WWTP, which receives streams from LTP2.

Taking into account the PFAS load measured at LTP1 and LTP2 as well as the PFAS load entering the investigated municipal WWTPs, it is possible to highlight that landfill leachate constitutes a significant source of PFAS for a receiving municipal WWTP. It is also noteworthy to observe that at LTP1 and at LTP2, landfill leachate is mixed with other liquid wastes before treatment. In contrast, LTP3 treats only landfill leachate, and in this plant were measured the highest PFAS concentrations. The treated leachate at LTP3 is discharged in the sewer network, which will collect this liquid waste to a municipal WWTP.

The advanced LTP N°3, which uses RO membranes, was able to obtain a permeate flux where none of the 30 target PFAS were detected (LOQ = 20 ng/L). These compounds were concentrated in the produced RO concentrate that showed a relatively high concentration of Σ PFAS ($62 \pm 17 \mu\text{g/L}$). Chemical-physical treatments implemented for treating RO concentrate were not able to remove these PFAS. The treated RO concentrate is then discharged into the sewage system together with the RO permeate. Hence, the flow from the concentrate treatment line nullified the complete removal of PFAS obtained by the RO filtration. Therefore, different treatments of RO concentrate are required for removing per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances and reaching the aim of “zero pollution”. Particularly, innovative treatments, including pyrolysis and plasma technologies, will be tested within

the PROMISCES research activities to obtain the complete destruction/removal of PFAS in RO concentrate.

In Bulgaria, ten regional landfills for municipal wastes that are representative for the country in terms of geographical distribution, age, and size were investigated to evaluate PFAS occurrence. The selected landfills collectively treat approximately 35% of the total waste that is landfilled in Bulgaria each year. The results show that the detected PFAS concentrations in untreated leachate are within the typical European range of 0.005 to 18 µg/L.

The Sofia landfill was studied in more detail to perform a mass flow analysis of PFAS during leachate treatment processes. The landfill of Sofia is the largest sanitary landfill in Bulgaria and treats waste from about 24% of the country's population. The leachate treatment technology is conventional, including mechanical and biological stages. The mass flow analysis showed high sensitivity in terms of correct determination of PFAS concentrations, especially with respect to the LOQ used. However, further research and improvements in analytical methods are needed to close the mass balance of PFAS during leachate treatment. In this study, chloride ions were used and proved to be a reliable inorganic element to verify the credibility of PFAS mass flow analysis.

Finally, even the Bulgarian PFAS mass flow analysis highlighted the need to develop new technological solutions to control and remove PFAS from landfill leachate to avoid its spreading into the environment.

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ANNEX 1: GC-MS method optimization

Optimization of chromatographic conditions: As a first step, using a standard solution of 10 mg/L TPSiF, a GC-MS method in SCAN mode was developed. A temperature program was optimized and the retention time of TPSiF was determined (6.49 min).

The GC-MS parameters are presented in Table A1.

Table A1: The GS-MS parameters

Column type	Rxi®-5Sil MS, Capillary, (fused silica) Crossbond, 5% diphenyl/95% dimethyl polysiloxane
Column dimensions, ID	30m*0.25mm
Elunet	He
Column temperature, °C	280
Temperature programme	50°C – 1 min., 270°C: 50 C/min, Run time: 12 min

Figure A1: Chromatogram of TPSiF in scan-mode GC-MS

The identity of TPSiF was confirmed by comparison of the experimental mass spectra with the mass spectra in the NIST library.

Figure A2: Experimental and NIST mass spectra of TPSiF

The established temperature program, retention time and molecular ions were used to develop a single ion monitoring method (SIM) and quantitative determination of TPSiF. The calibration of the SIM method was performed with standard solutions in the range from 1 µg/L to 1000 µg/L (see Figure A2).

Figure A3: Calibration graph of TPSiF from 1 µg/L to 1000 µg/L.

ANNEX 2: Development of a procedure for defluorination and fluoride derivatization

As a next step, a sample preparation procedure was optimized: defluorination of PFOA and PFDA with SBP and derivatization with TSiOH to obtain of TPSiF. The reactions that take place are presented in Figure A4.

Figure A4: Defluorination and derivatization procedures

The defluorination procedure was conducted as follows: 6 mL of 0.000072M PFOA (29.8 mg/L), dissolved in AcN was mixed with 3.00 mL SBP in a 50 mL polypropylene test tube. The tube was kept closed for 1 hour to conduct defluorination. Then, 6.00 mL of water was added and the mixture was shaken on a rotator for 2 hours. The organic and aqueous layers were separated by centrifugation for 10 min at 3600 rpm.

The derivatization procedure was done as follows: 6 mL of the aqueous phase was decanted and transferred in a 50 mL polypropylene test tube. Then 6 mL 0.000036M TPSiOH, 3 ml conc. HClO₄ and 3 mL heptane were added. The closed vessels were vigorously agitated using a vortex for approximately 2 hours at room temperature. An aliquot of the heptane layer was decanted and analyzed in a series of dilutions. An example of the obtained chromatogram is presented on Figure A5.

Figure A5: A chromatogram of TPSiF, obtained after defluorination and derivatization of PFOA.

The theoretical concentration of TPSiF was calculated considering that the molar interaction ratio of PFOA:TPSiF is 1:15 (PFDA:TPSiF 1:17) and a two-fold concentration was made (6mL PFOA/PFDA in acetonitrile:3mL heptane).

The theoretical concentration of TPSiF should be:

$$n(\text{PFOA}) = C_M * V = 0.000072\text{M} * 0.006\text{L} = 4.32 * 10^{-7} \text{ mol}$$

$$n(\text{TPSiF}) = 4.32 * 10^{-7} * 15 = 6.48 * 10^{-6} \text{ mol}$$

$$n(\text{TPSiF}) = m/M_w \leftrightarrow m = n * M_w = 6.48 * 10^{-6} * 278.4 = 0.0018 \text{ g} = 1.80 \text{ mg}$$

$$\text{Concentration TPSiF (mg/L)} = 1.80 \text{ mg}/0.003\text{L} = 601 \text{ mg/L}$$

The measurement was made after a series of calibration. A chromatogram after a dilution 1-200 is presented on Fig. 5. dilution, therefore the theoretical concentration is 3.00 mg/L. According to measurement data, the obtained concentration of TPSiF is 2.88 mg/L, which represents 96% recovery.

The experiment was performed in 6 replicates and the recoveries ranged from 92 to 101%.

ANNEX 3: PFAS in untreated leachate in 10 landfills, LOQ 1 µg/L

µg/L	Sofia	Burgas	Stara Zagora	Stara Zagora	Pleven	Pleven	Pernik	Pernik	Blagoevgrad	Blagoevgrad	Vratsa	Vratsa	Gabrovo	Gabrovo	Lovech	Lovech	Zlatitsa	Zlatitsa
	30.Oct	Nov	Sept	Nov	Sept	Nov	Sept	Nov	Sept	Nov	Sept	Nov	Sept	Nov	Sept	Nov	Sept	Nov
PFBA	1,5	<	3,0	1,4	<	<	1,0	<	1,0	<	<	<	1,0	1,1	<	1,0	<	<
PFPeA	1,6	1,2	<	1,1	<	<	<	1,2	<	1,1	<	<	<	1,3	<	1,7	<	<
4-2 FTS	0,2	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<
PFHxA	2,2	1,0	3,0	1,7	<	<	5,0	2,4	4,0	2,0	<	1,1	5,0	1,8	3,0	1,9	2,0	<
PFBS	2,9	4,2	8,0	6,7	<	<	6,0	3,0	4,0	<	<	<	4,0	2,0	2,0	1,5	2,0	<
PFOA	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	1,7	<	<
PFOS	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	1,0	<	<
Σ PFAS µg/L	8,4	6,4	14,0	10,9	< LOQ	< LOQ	12,0	6,6	9,0	3,1	< LOQ	1,1	10,0	6,2	5,0	8,8	4,0	< LOQ

ANNEX 4: PFAS at the sampling points of the Sofia leachate treatment plant

LOQ µg/L		Sampling point 1	Sampling point 2										
		30/10/2023	14/11/2023	29/11/23	11/12/23	28/12/23	09/01/24	30/10/2023	14/11/2023	29/11/23	11/12/23	28/12/23	09/01/24
0,1	4-2 FTS	<	<	<	<	not measured	<	0,2	<	<	<	0,2	<
1	PFBA	<	<	<	<	not measured	0,5	1,5	<	<	<	0,4	0,4
0,1	PFBS	<	<	<	<	not measured	0,2	2,9	<	1,3	1,7	0,8	0,9
0,1	PFHpA	<	<	<	<	not measured	0,1	<	<	<	<	0,1	0,1
1	PFHpS	<	<	<	<	not measured	<	<	<	<	<	<	<
1	PFHxA	<	<	<	<	not measured	0,3	2,2	<	1,0	1,6	0,9	0,9
1	PFOA	<	<	<	<	not measured	0,1	<	<	<	<	0,2	0,2
0,1	PFOS	<	<	<	<	not measured	<	<	<	<	<	<	<
1	PFPeA	<	<	<	<	not measured	0,2	1,6	<	<	1,1	0,6	0,6
	SOMMA	< LOQ	< LOQ	< LOQ	< LOQ	0,0	1,4	8,4	< LOQ	2,3	4,4	3,2	3,1

LOQ µg/L		Sampling point 4	Sampling point 7										
		30/10/2023	14/11/2023	29/11/23	11/12/23	28/12/23	09/01/24	30/10/2023	14/11/2023	29/11/23	11/12/23	28/12/23	09/01/24
0,1	4-2 FTS	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<
1	PFBA	<	<	<	<	0,2	0,2	<	<	<	<	0,4	0,3
0,1	PFBS	1,0	<	<	<	0,5	0,6	1,2	1,2	1,6	1,0	0,6	0,7
0,1	PFHpA	<	<	<	<	0,1	0,1	<	<	<	<	0,1	0,1
1	PFHpS	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<
1	PFHxA	<	<	<	<	0,5	0,4	<	<	<	<	0,6	0,4
1	PFOA	<	<	<	<	0,1	0,1	<	<	<	<	0,2	0,1
0,1	PFOS	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<
1	PFPeA	<	<	<	<	0,4	0,3	1,0	1,1	1,0	<	0,5	0,5
	SOMMA	1,0	< LOQ	< LOQ	0,0	1,8	1,7	2,2	2,3	2,6	1,0	2,4	2,1

LOQ µg/L		Sampling point 3	Sampling point 6										
		30/10/2023	14/11/2023	29/11/23	11/12/23	28/12/23	09/01/24	30/10 /2023	14/11 /2023	29/11/23	11/12/23	28/12/23	09/01/24
0,02	4-2 FTS	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<
0,02	PFBA	0,09	0,03	0,08	0,09	0,07	0,08	0,10	0,04	0,03	0,03	0,02	0,02
0,02	PFBS	0,56	0,16	0,53	0,55	0,45	0,40	0,49	0,14	0,15	0,16	0,11	0,11
0,02	PFHpA	0,03	<	0,03	0,03	0,02	0,03	0,03	<	<	<	<	<
0,02	PFHpS	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<
0,02	PFHxA	0,16	0,05	0,14	0,16	0,12	0,13	0,13	0,05	0,05	0,04	0,04	0,03
0,02	PFOA	0,03	<	0,03	0,04	0,02	0,02	0,03	<	<	<	0,02	0,02
0,02	PFOS	0,06	0,03	0,06	0,06	0,05	0,04	0,06	0,04	0,03	0,03	0,02	0,02
0,02	PFPeA	0,25	0,08	0,24	0,27	0,20	0,23	0,23	0,09	0,08	0,08	0,06	0,06
	SOMMA	1,18	0,35	1,11	1,20	0,93	0,93	1,07	0,36	0,34	0,34	0,27	0,26

